

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

D5: Summary report on the evaluation of the inter-laboratory comparison performed with the ERM and gCRMs: including information on the repeatability and reproducibility of the data and an evaluation of the major uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting, according to the EN 16516 test method

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Summary

This is a summary report of the results obtained in the workshop and inter-laboratory comparison (ILC) of gaseous certified reference materials (gCRMs, ILC part 1) and the ILC of emission reference materials (ERMs, ILC part 2). It includes information on the repeatability and reproducibility of the data and the major uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting of the results. The gCRMs and ERMs were developed in the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air (20NRM04 MetrIAQ).

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1 Introduction

Considering that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of these emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection.

The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (*Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air*) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Within the framework of the MetrIAQ project a workshop and an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) were organised. The ILC involved 2 parts:

- Part 1: Analysis of gCRMs
- Part 2: Emission test chamber method

During the **workshop** participants could take samples from a dynamic gas mixture using their own sampling pumps and sorbent tubes.

The aim of the workshop was to assess the capability of laboratories to sample and measure VOCs relevant in emissions from building materials. The results of the participants were processed as described below for part 1 of the ILC [Annex 1].

The aim of **part 1** of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed gCRM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents relevant for emissions from building materials. The ILC protocol describes how the ILC was performed [Annex 2]. Furthermore, a guideline for the preparation and analysis of the developed gCRMs is available online as a project deliverable [2].

The evaluation of the results is performed using *zeta* scores (ζ) as described in ISO 13528 [3]. The reference values were determined by VSL by verification of the mass sampled into the sorbent tubes according to ISO 12963 [4]. For the performance rating, the reference values were used as assigned values save for *n*-hexane for which the consensus value was used. A report on the preparation, verification and participant results was written [Annex 3].

The aim of **part 2** of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed ERM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents released from materials in the emission test chamber procedure. The ERMs are either impregnated porous materials produced by BAM, or μ -capsules filled with VOC produced by FhG. Four VOCs (*n*-hexane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene) were used to

produce the ERMs. The protocol in Annex 4 explains how the ILC part 2 was performed. A report on the preparation, uncertainty, storage and stability and the participant results was written [Annex 5].

This report gives an evaluation of the results obtained during workshop and ILC part 1 and part 2, including information regarding the repeatability and reproducibility of the data and the major uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting of the results.

2 Repeatability and reproducibility of the samples and measurements

2.1 Workshop

During the workshop the participants performed the sampling of their own tubes, therefore it is not possible to give a conclusion on the repeatability and reproducibility of the samples obtained.

During the workshop multiple tubes were sampled for each lab. The repeatability standard deviations of the measurement results for each lab were determined (Table 1). The reproducibility of measurement results could not be determined as only one batch of samples was analysed during the ILC.

Table 1 – Standard deviation (Stdev) and expanded uncertainty (U, $k = 2$) measurement results participants in nanograms (ng). Lab 3 only reported one result, therefore the repeatability could not be determined.

Lab →	5		8		9	
VOC ↓	Stdev	U	Stdev	U	Stdev	U
n-Hexane	12	14	2.4	32	11	63
MIBK	1.4	8	0.4	15	7	66
Toluene	1.4	7	1.3	14	8	59
Butyl acetate	0.7	6	0.1	9	5	39
Cyclohexanone	2.1	12	0.4	22	6	44
o-Xylene	2.8	11	0.7	17	7	71
Phenol	2.1	5	1.8	30	5	27
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	0.7	6	1.3	15	6	56

The standard deviations calculated are all within the uncertainty reported by the participants indicating they also took other uncertainty sources into account next to the measurement standard deviation. The standard deviations for n-hexane are larger compared to those for other VOCs, this could be caused by the volatility of n-hexane. The calculated standard deviations for Lab 9 are much for all VOCs compared to the other two participants. Nevertheless, lab 9 performed satisfactory in both the workshop and ILC as they reported higher uncertainties compared to the other participants.

In the workshop report, a value for the excess standard deviation (τ) was determined. T indicates that there are substantial differences between the reported results. None of the data sets is mutually consistent [Annex 1].

2.2 ILC part 1

For part 1 of the ILC, the participants' tubes were sampled in different series and the homogeneity between the different series was determined (Figure 1, Table 2). The homogeneity can also be considered as the repeatability of the sampling process. Together with the ILC participants' tubes, 2 VSL tubes were sampled,

simultaneously. The tubes were analysed by VSL to determine the reference values. The peak area of each component is shown for the 2 tubes sampled simultaneously with the participants' tubes. The results of lab 1 deviate because these tubes were sampled four weeks after sampling of the other tubes. Lab 3 did not participate in the ILC, only in the workshop. The homogeneity for n-hexane could not be determined as there was a problem with the stability of n-hexane on the tubes [see Annex 3].

Figure 1 – Verification results of the ILC participants' tubes

Table 2 – Standard deviation verification sampling series

VOC	Stdev (%)
MIBK	2.6
Toluene	1.9
Butyl acetate	1.9
Cyclohexanone	3.3
o-Xylene	2.1
Phenol	8
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	2.5

The standard deviations are well within the relative expanded uncertainty of 5% for the reference values of the VOC mass sampled save for phenol which has a relative expanded measurement uncertainty of 20%. Based on these results it can be concluded that the different sample series were prepared homogeneously, and the repeatability of the sample preparation is within the uncertainty of the reference value. It was not possible to determine the repeatability for the ILC as the sampling was only repeated once. The repeatability of the gas mixture

preparation, sampling and measurements will be discussed in D6 "Report on the preparation and measurement uncertainty of ERMs, gPRM and gCRMs".

During ILC part 1, multiple tubes were also sampled for each participant. The repeatability standard deviations of the measurement results were determined (Table 3). The reproducibility of measurement results could not be determined as only one batch of samples was analysed during the ILC.

Table 3 – Standard deviation (S) and expanded uncertainty (U, $k = 2$) measurement results participants in nanograms (ng). Lab 9 only provided the result for 1 tube, therefore the standard deviation could not be determined.

Lab →	1		2		4		5		6		7		8	
VOC ↓	S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U
n-Hexane	3.2	10	0.7	19	142	145	12	13	6	39	2.9	15	7	26
MIBK	4	13	0.2	20	10	57	1.4	7	1.0	30	2.6	18	0.2	13
Toluene	2.5	13	3.7	20	10	54	1.4	6	1.7	27	2.9	15	1.9	12
Butyl acetate	1.7	8	1.3	11	5	40	0.7	6	0.6	21	2.9	14	1.0	8
Cyclohexanone	3.2	11	28	19	9	40	2.1	10	0.6	24	3.6	14	2.4	20
o-Xylene	2.1	15	6.4	24	7	64	2.8	10	1.7	30	2.8	19	0.6	15
Phenol	1.2	9	2.5	6	8	22	2.1	4	0.6	11			1.2	31
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	4	11	21	18	10	53	0.7	5	1.5	23	2.8	17	0.7	13

The calculated standard deviations for ILC part 1 show the same trends as for the workshop. Most of the standard deviations calculated are within the uncertainty reported by the participants. Lab 2 reported a smaller uncertainty for cyclohexanone and 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene compared to the standard deviation. Furthermore, lab 4 and lab 5 reported standard deviations and uncertainties very close to each other for n-hexane. Finally, the standard deviations calculated for lab 7 are all $> \frac{1}{2}U$, this indicates that they did not take into account other uncertainty sources. The standard deviations of lab 4, 5, 6 and 8 for n-hexane are larger compared to those for other VOCs.

In the ILC report, a value for the excess standard deviation (τ) was determined. τ indicates that there are substantial differences between the reported results for MIBK, toluene and phenol [Annex 3].

2.3 ILC part 2

Since the herein used ERMs are no primary reference materials, it is not possible to easily determine the measurement uncertainty, or parts of it, such as the repeatability or reproducibility, reference values etc., based on the generation procedure. The measurement uncertainty needs to be determined by measuring the ERMs in an emission test chamber. Thus, the uncertainty will consist of the uncertainty of the analysis, sampling, operational parameters of the emission test chamber and the ERM. Some parts of it can be isolated (such as the analysis and sampling). Other parts, such as the uncertainty of the emission test chamber and the ERM, cannot be isolated from each other. In addition, a lot of chambers and/or a long period of time are needed to conduct enough measurements for statistical significance.

For ILC part 2, we differentiate between in-batch repeatability (consecutive measurements of an ERM from the same batch by **one** laboratory), batch-to-batch repeatability (measurements of different batches of the same ERM by **one** laboratory), in-batch reproducibility (measurements of an ERM from the same batch by many different laboratories) and batch-to-batch reproducibility (measurements of different batches of the same ERM by different laboratories). Further differentiation can be done between short-term and long-term repeatability. Here, we only refer to the long-term repeatability. It was found that the repeatability is often slightly better, but still similar to the reproducibility. Thus, one can be used to estimate the other.

Parts of these values were obtained during the ILC part 2, others during material development and internal validation. The repeatability/reproducibility is highly dependent on the specific ERM (Table 4).

Table 4 – values of in-batch and batch-to-batch repeatability/reproducibility of ERMs given as relative standard deviation.

ERM / granules, powders and μ -capsules	In-batch rep. of the ER 14 days after loading [%]			Batch-to-batch rep. of the ER 14 days after loading [%]
	a	b	c	a
C 40/4 [toluene]	17	18		39
C 40/4 [2-ethyl-1-hexanol]		66	31	15
C 45/4 [n-hexane]			26	18
C 45/4 [toluene]			22	28
BEA [n-hexane]		57		9
BEA [toluene]				12
BEA [2-ethyl-1-hexanol]				12
μ -capsules HDTTL [D-limonene]		36	47	

^a Repeatability, taken from development. ^b Reproducibility, taken from ILC part 2. ^c Repeatability, taken from internal validation.

The batch-to-batch repeatability is not very good in general. The best batch-to-batch repeatability was found for BEA impregnated with *n*-hexane, though the in-batch reproducibility of that ERM is worse than that of some other materials. Materials with a very good in-batch repeatability (such as C 40/4 impregnated with toluene) exhibit a rather poor batch-to-batch repeatability. However, the in-batch reproducibility is much more important, because the batch-to-batch reproducibility can be easily circumvented by producing very big batches of ERM. In a study on long-term stability it was proven, that the ERMs are quite stable, so that large batches of ERM can be produced, characterised, and used for up to 12 months.

3 Uncertainty sources

3.1 Workshop and ILC part 1

Participants were asked to report the uncertainty evaluation for their results obtained in the workshop and ILC part 1. Several participants take into account only the standard deviation or measurement uncertainty based on the precision, trueness and accuracy of the method or the standard deviation. Other also took into account purity of the VOCs, uncertainty for the liquid handling including uncertainty of the balance, pipettes and flasks used for calibration, uncertainty of μL -syringe for spiking.

3.2 ILC part 2

The participants were asked to report the uncertainty evaluation for their results obtained in ILC part 2. Most evaluations lack differentiation between analysis, sampling, and the emission test chamber procedure, as well as dependency on substance and concentration. A list of uncertainty sources and hints is provided.

4 Application of the EMR and gCRM according to EN 16516

4.1 gCRM

The gCRM developed is based on the check material described in section 8.2.2.3 “Checks on analytical system performance” of EN 16516 [1]. The check material is a chromatographic test mix containing VOCs that are representative of the range of compounds of interest for indoor air quality. The EN 16516 check material contains at least *n*-hexane, MIBK, toluene, butyl acetate, cyclohexanone, *o*-xylene, phenol, 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene and *n*-hexadecane. The composition of the check material is adjusted, 1,2,3-trimethylbenzene is replaced by 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene and *n*-hexadecane is not used. It is difficult to purchase or obtain 1,2,3-TMB with a purity above 90 %. This has consequences for the reference material production and the measurements performed with the reference materials. VOC *n*-hexadecane is omitted as this compound, with a boiling point of 287 °C and vapour pressure of 0.0025 kPa, cannot be produced as a gas mixture in the same way as the other VOCs.

With the use of the gCRM in the ILC it was shown that this reference material can be used for this application and as a check material according to EN 16516 section 8.2.2.3. These reference materials are traceable to the international standards and therefore primary standards as required by the EN 16516 (section 8.4.2). For some of the VOCs in the check material, *n*-hexane, toluene, *o*-xylene and 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene, VSL holds Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMC) represented in the Key Comparison Database (KCDB) as part of the Mutual Recognition Arrangement (MRA) of the International Committee of Weights and Measures (CIPM). For the other VOCs, MIBK, butyl acetate, cyclohexanone and phenol, VSL will submit CMCs based on the results obtained in the MetrIAQ project.

4.2 ERM

The purpose of ERMs is to evaluate the performance of the emission test chamber procedure. External reference materials are needed to proof the compliance with quality requirements for laboratories seeking accreditation according to EN 16516 – chapter 8.5.2 [1] and ISO 16000 series [5-8]. Further, the participation of interlaboratory comparisons is advised according to EN 16516 – chapter 8.2.2.6 [1]. These ILCs can also be performed with help of ERMs. The emission rate and decline of emission profile needs to be known [1].

The ERMs developed within the project can be used for this purpose. However, the performance of the ERMs is quite diverse. Some materials are almost ready for application, while others need further development.

5 Conclusion

The workshop and ILC part 1 and part 2 were performed to validate the ERM and gCRM developed in the MetrIAQ project.

The ILCs showed that the ERM and gCRM are suitable for this use. Based on the results obtained in the ILCs laboratories were able to assess their capabilities to sample and measure VOCs relevant in emissions from building materials. This paved the way to set up similar ILCs using these reference materials in the future.

While a few ERMs, loaded with single VOCs, are almost ready for application, further development is needed to broaden the scope for other VOCs.

In combination with the short and long-term stability studies on the reference products (refer to deliverables D2 and D3 of this project) the aims of objective 3 have been fully fulfilled.

References

1. EN 16516:2017, Construction products – Assessment of release of dangerous substances – Determination of emissions into indoor air.
2. I. de Krom, E. Henderson, A.M.H. van der Veen, A. Baldan, F. Maes, Guideline for the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants stated in the EU-LCI list with relative uncertainties below 5 % ($k = 2$) and a shelf life of at least 1 year, 2023, [20NRM04-MetrIAQ A1.3.5 VSL Deliverable-report-D3 Final.pdf](#)
3. ISO 13528:2022, Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison.
4. ISO 12963:2017, Gas analysis – Comparison methods for the determination of the composition of gas mixtures based on one- and two-point calibration.
5. ISO 16000-3:2021, Indoor Air – Part 3: Determination of formaldehyde and other carbonyl compounds – Active sampling method.
6. ISO 16000-6:2021, Indoor air - Part 6: Determination of organic compounds (VVOC, VOC, SVOC) in indoor and test chamber air by active sampling on sorbent tubes, thermal desorption and gas chromatography using MS or MS FID.
7. ISO 16000-9:2023, Indoor air – Part 9: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing - Emission test chamber method.
8. ISO 16000-11:2006, Indoor air - Part 11: Determination of the emission of volatile organic compounds from building products and furnishing - Sampling, storage of samples and preparation of test specimens.

Annexes

Annex 1: Report workshop sampling and analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled onto sorbent tubes

Annex 2: Protocol for the interlaboratory comparison for the analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled into sorbent tubes

Annex 3: Report interlaboratory comparison for the analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled onto sorbent tubes

Annex 4: Protocol for the inter-laboratory comparison (ILC part 2) for the measurement of emission reference materials (ERM)

Annex 5: Report on the inter-laboratory comparison (ILC part 2) for the measurement of emission reference materials (ERM)

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

Annex 1: Report on workshop sampling and analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled onto sorbent tubes

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1 Introduction

Considering that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of these emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection. The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Within the framework of the project MetrIAQ, a workshop was organised. During the workshop participants could take samples from a dynamic gas mixtures using their own sampling pumps and sorbent tubes.

The aim of the workshop was to assess the capability of laboratories to sample and measure VOCs relevant in emissions from building materials.

The evaluation of the results is performed using Zeta scores (ζ) as described in ISO 13528 [2]. The reference values were determined by VSL, by verification of the mass sampled into the sorbent tubes according to ISO 12963 [3]. These reference value were used as assigned values for the performance rating.

2 Participants

A total of 4 labs participated in the workshop (Table 1). In this report the results of the labs are exclusively referred to by means of their anonymous lab code.

Table 1 – Participants workshop

Organisation	Country
BAM	Germany
Eco-Institute	Germany
Knauf	Germany
VITO	Belgium

3 Workshop samples

3.1 Preparation dynamic gas mixture

Project partner VITO prepared a dynamic gas mixture containing selected VOCs in air according to ISO 6145-4 (Table 2) [4].

Table 2 – Selected VOCs

VOC	CAS number
n-Hexane	110-54-3
Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	108-10-1
Toluene	108-88-3
Butyl acetate	123-86-4
Cyclohexanone	108-94-1
o-Xylene	95-47-6
Phenol	108-95-2
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	108-67-8

The dynamic generation of gaseous VOCs at indoor air level concentrations (and at occupational hygiene levels) in a carrier gas throughout a glass distribution line is achieved by fluid injection through a capillary according to ISO 6145-4 [4]. The fluid, a metrologically traceable solution of the VOCs, is thermally heated, evaporated and injected dynamically into the carrier gas stream.

The main components of the capillary dosage unit are the capillary (glass or a deactivated fused silica column), a pressure reducer and a stainless-steel housing. A pressure difference between both ends of the capillary forces the liquid through it. At the upper end of the capillary, the fluid is flash-heated and evaporated. The resulting vapour is dynamically injected into a primary flow of mass flow controlled nitrogen. This flow enters at the low pressure side of the capillary and transports the evaporated mixture to a Mass Flow Controller to take an aliquot and transfer it into the nitrogen carrier gas stream in the distribution line. The reservoir containing the liquid is placed on analytical balance which allows a continuous measurement of liquid consumption at any time during its injection process. Furthermore, the stability of the generated gas mixture is measured by an online GC-FID system equipped with an injection loop and total hydrocarbon analyser.

The technique of capillary dosage is theoretically based on Poiseuille's equation which allows the calculation of a laminar flow through a cylindrical tube with radius r . For a pressure difference Δp over a length l , the fluid flow is calculated according to equation (1).

$$Qv = \Delta p \pi r^4 / 8Nl \quad (1)$$

where:

Δp : pressure drop across a cylindrical tube ($N\ m^{-2}$)

r : internal tube radius (m)

l : the tube length (m)

N : the dynamic viscosity ($kg\ ms^{-1}$)

Qv : the fluid flow ($m^3\ s^{-1}$)

The VOC concentrations ($\mu g\ m^{-3}$) are calculated using the mass loss of the mixture in the reservoir ($\mu g\ min^{-1}$) and the different mass flow controlled nitrogen flows ($m^3\ min^{-1}$), which are all calibrated with primary flow meters and corrected to standard conditions (101.315 kPa and 293.15 K). The total gas concentration of

the mixture is recalculated to the individual VOCs by using the weight ratios of each VOC in the mixture.

3.2 Sampling by the participants

All the participants sampled their tubes from the dynamic gas mixture, according to ISO 16017-1, with a flow of 100 ml min⁻¹ for a time of 10 minutes [5].

3.3 Reference value

The reference values for the VOC masses sampled into the tubes was determined by project partner VSL against primary gaseous reference gas mixtures prepared. In the MetrIAQ project a report was published on the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants [6].

For the workshop a calibration gas mixture containing the selected VOCs in dry, clean air was prepared by VSL according to ISO 6145-4 [4]. The calibration gas mixture was sampled into sorbent tubes according to ISO 16017-1 [5]. These were used to verify tubes sampled during the workshop to determine the reference values according to ISO 12963 [3] (Table 3). Based on the calibration the workshop reference value was calculated according to equation (2).

$$m_{ILC} = \frac{m_{i(dynamic)} A_{ILC}}{A_{i(dynamic)}} \quad (2)$$

Where:

m_{ILC} : mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube based on the verification (ng)

$m_{i(dynamic)}$: mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube from the dynamic gPRM used for calibration (ng)

A_{ILC} : peak area of VOC i for the ILC

$A_{i(dynamic)}$: peak area of VOC i for the dynamic gPRM

Table 3 – Workshop reference values (m) and associated expanded uncertainty $U(m)$

VOC	m (ng)	$U(m)$ (ng) ($k = 2$)
n-Hexane	107.23	5.36
MIBK	137.90	6.89
Toluene	128.47	6.42
Butyl acetate	85.79	4.29
Cyclohexanone	121.93	6.10
o-Xylene	161.89	8.09
Phenol	99.09	4.95
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	137.58	6.88

4 Results of the participants

4.1 Evaluation of the results

The zeta scores for the assessment of laboratory results obtained in the framework of proficiency testing are calculated using to the equation (3) according to ISO 13528 [2].

$$\zeta_{lab(i)} = \frac{m_{lab(i)} - m_{ref(i)}}{\sqrt{u_{lab(i)}^2 + u_{ref(i)}^2}} \quad \text{eq. (3)}$$

Where:

$\zeta_{lab(i)}$: zeta score of the participating laboratory for VOC i

$m_{lab(i)}$: laboratory result (i.e., the laboratory mean value) for the mass of VOC i in the sorbent tube (ng).

$m_{ref(i)}$: reference value for the mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube (ng)

$u_{lab(i)}^2$: standard uncertainty of the result from the participant for the mass of VOC i in the sorbent tube (ng)

$u_{ref(i)}^2$: standard uncertainty of the reference value for the mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube (ng)

The interpretation of the zeta scores is similar to that of Z -scores and is as follows [2]:

$ \zeta \leq 2.0$	satisfactory result
$2.0 < \zeta < 3.0$	questionable result
$ \zeta \geq 3.0$	unsatisfactory result

4.2 Consensus values

The consensus values were calculated using the reported data from all participants (Table 4). A random effects model was used, which was fitted using restricted maximum likelihood [7-9]. An uncertainty component was included to account for the fact that not all results were mutually consistent.

Table 4 – Consensus values (m), associated standard uncertainties ($u(m)$) and the excess standard deviation (τ) for the masses (ng)

Component	m	$u(m)$	τ
n-Hexane	121.800	20.674	28.472
MIBK	133.898	15.480	21.533

Component	m	$u(m)$	τ
Toluene	123.974	14.301	20.035
Butyl acetate	84.233	9.293	12.230
Cyclohexanone	113.549	7.738	0.000
o-Xylene	154.469	9.780	7.086
Phenol	68.797	4.498	0.000
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	130.749	11.059	13.428

The consensus values were calculated from the complete data sets. The values for the excess standard deviation τ indicate that there are substantial differences between the reported results. None of the data sets (see also section 4.3) is mutually consistent.

4.3 Evaluation Laboratory results

The reported results for the mass n-hexane are shown in Figure 1 and the zeta scores in Figure 2.

Figure 1 – Reported results for the mass n-hexane

Figure 2 – Zeta scores for the mass n-hexane

The reported results for the mass MIBK are shown in Figure 3 and the zeta scores in Figure 4.

Figure 3 – Reported results for the mass MIBK

Figure 4 – Zeta scores for the mass MIBK

The reported results for the mass toluene are shown in Figure 5 and the zeta scores in Figure 6.

Figure 5 – Reported results for the mass toluene

Figure 6 – Zeta scores for the mass toluene

The reported results for the mass butyl acetate are shown in Figure 7 and the zeta scores in Figure 8.

Figure 7 – Reported results for the mass butyl acetate

Figure 8 – Zeta scores for the mass butyl acetate

The reported results for the mass cyclohexanone are shown in Figure 9 and the zeta scores in Figure 10.

Figure 9 – Reported results for the mass cyclohexanone

Figure 10 – Zeta scores for the mass cyclohexanone

The reported results for the mass o-xylene are shown in Figure 11 and the zeta scores in Figure 12.

Figure 11 – Reported results for the mass o-xylene

Figure 12 – Zeta scores for the mass o-xylene

The reported results for the mass phenol are shown in Figure 13 and the zeta scores in Figure 14.

Figure 13 – Reported results for the mass phenol

Figure 14 – Zeta scores for the mass phenol

The reported results for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene are shown in Figure 15 and the zeta scores in Figure 16.

Figure 15 – Reported results for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

Figure 16 – Zeta scores for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

5 Conclusion

The MetrIAQ workshop was carried out to assess the participants capabilities in sampling and measuring VOCs, relevant in emissions from building materials, in sorbent tubes. The results obtained in this workshop are satisfactory for two out of the four labs (3 and 9). They only obtained questionable results for phenol. However, all four labs obtained negative Zeta-scores for phenol. This could indicate that the reference value for phenol is too high. Lab 8 performed satisfactory for all components save from n-hexane for which they performed unsatisfactory. Finally, lab 5 reported questionable results for MIBK and toluene and biased results for phenol and 1,3,5-TMB.

References

1. EN 16516:2017 Construction products – Assessment of release of dangerous substances – Determination of emissions into indoor air.
2. ISO 13528:2022 Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison.
3. ISO 12963:2017 Gas analysis – Comparison methods for the determination of the composition of gas mixtures based on one- and two-point calibration.
4. ISO 6145-4:2004 Gas analysis – Preparation of calibration gas mixtures using dynamic volumetric methods – part 4: Continuous syringe injection method.
5. ISO 16017-1:2000 Indoor, ambient and workplace air sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by sorbent tube/thermal desorption/capillary gas chromatograph – Part 1: Pumped sampling.
6. I. de Krom, E. Henderson, A.M.H. van der Veen, A. Baldan, F. Maes, Guideline for the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants stated in the EU-LCI list with relative uncertainties below 5 % ($k = 2$) and a shelf life of at least 1 year, 2023, <https://zenodo.org/records/10656469>
7. Viechtbauer, W. (2010). Conducting meta-analyses in R with the metafor package. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 36(3), 1-48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v036.i03>
8. Viechtbauer, W. (2005). Bias and efficiency of meta-analytic variance estimators in the random-effects model. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 30(3), 261–293. <https://doi.org/10.3102/10769986030003261>
9. Raudenbush, S. W. (2009). Analyzing effect sizes: Random effects models. In H. Cooper, L. V. Hedges, & J. C. Valentine (Eds.), *The handbook of research synthesis and meta-analysis* (2nd ed., pp. 295–315). New York: Russell Sage Foundation.

Annex A: laboratory results and evaluation

Table 6 – Reported results for the mass n-hexane

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	135.0	31.28	107.228	5.361	1.750
5	89.0	13.00	107.228	5.361	-0.564
8	158.1	31.70	107.228	5.361	3.165
9	151.0	63.00	107.228	5.361	1.385

Table 7 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass MIBK

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	154.0	35.682	137.897	6.895	0.886
5	112.0	7.000	137.897	6.895	-2.064
8	152.2	15.200	137.897	6.895	1.714
9	157.0	66.000	137.897	6.895	0.576

Table 8 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass toluene

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	139.0	32.206	128.469	6.423	0.641
5	104.0	6.000	128.469	6.423	-2.414
8	142.5	14.300	128.469	6.423	1.790
9	142.0	59.000	128.469	6.423	0.456

Table 9 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass butyl acetate

Lab	Value(ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	Ref(ng)	Ref. <i>U</i> (ng)	zeta
3	103.0	23.865	85.786	4.289	1.420
5	71.0	6.000	85.786	4.289	-1.298
8	93.6	9.400	85.786	4.289	1.513
9	94.0	39.000	85.786	4.289	0.419

Table 10 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass cyclohexanone

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	115.0	26.646	121.931	6.097	-0.507
5	115.0	12.000	121.931	6.097	-0.435
8	112.5	11.300	121.931	6.097	-0.826
9	106.0	44.000	121.931	6.097	-0.717

Table 11 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass o-xylene

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	166	38.462	161.889	8.094	0.209
5	146	10.000	161.889	8.094	-1.595
8	170	17.000	161.889	8.094	0.862
9	170	71.000	161.889	8.094	0.227

Table 12 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass phenol

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	73	16.914	99.092	4.955	-2.961
5	68	5.000	99.092	4.955	-8.266
8	74	14.800	99.092	4.955	-1.650
9	64	27.000	99.092	4.955	-2.557

Table 13 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
3	149.0	34.523	137.578	6.879	0.649
5	119.0	6.000	137.578	6.879	-3.632
8	146.5	14.700	137.578	6.879	1.099
9	135.0	56.000	137.578	6.879	-0.091

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

Annex 2: Protocol for the interlaboratory comparison for the analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled into sorbent tubes

Authors: Iris de Krom¹, Wouter van der Hout¹, Adriaan van der Veen¹, Frederick Maes²

Lead partner: **VSL**¹

Other partners: VITO²

Version date: 29 March 2023

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1 Introduction

Given that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products, into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of the emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection. The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Within the framework of the project this interlaboratory comparison (ILC) is organised containing 2 parts:

- Part 1: Analysis of gCRMs, described in this protocol
- Part 2: Emission test chamber method, described in a separate protocol

The aim of the part 1 of the ILC is 1) to validate the developed gCRM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOCs relevant in emissions from building materials.

More information about the preparation and analysis of developed gCRMs has been reported in a project deliverable available online [2].

2 Samples

2.1 Participant sorbent tubes

Each participant will send VITO four clean (conditioned) ready-for-use sorbent tubes, with Tenax TA® as sorbent material. Three for sampling with the VOC gas mixture

2.2 Preparation

Project partner VITO will prepare a dynamic gas mixture containing selected VOCs in air according to ISO 6145-4 (Table 1) [3]. The gas mixture will be sampled into sorbent tubes provided by the participants according to ISO 16017-1 [4].

Table 1: Selected VOCs

VOC	CAS number
n-Hexane	110-54-3
Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	108-10-1
Toluene	108-88-3
Butyl acetate	123-86-4
Cyclohexanone	108-94-1

o-Xylene	95-47-6
Phenol	108-95-2
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	108-67-8

The mass per VOC per sorbent tube is in the range of 50 ng – 150 ng.

2.3 Homogeneity study

VITO will conduct a homogeneity study to determine all participant sorbent tubes contain equal masses of the VOCs.

2.4 Reference value

The reference values for the VOC masses sampled into the tubes will be determined by project partner VSL against primary gaseous reference gas mixtures prepared. A calibration gas mixture containing the selected VOCs in dry, clean air will be prepared by VSL according to ISO 6145-4 [3]. The calibration gas mixture will be sampled into sorbent tubes according to ISO 16017-1 [4]. These will be used to verify tubes sampled during the ILC to determine the reference values according to ISO 12963 [5]. The expanded uncertainty of the masses of the certified components will be between 5% and 10%.

2.5 Sample handling

After sampling of the sorbent tubes they will be returned to the participants for analysis and quantification of the VOCs. The participants are requested to analyse the sample according to their default laboratory procedure.

Store the sampled sorbent tubes at room temperature in a clean environment before analysis. The participants will analyse the sorbent tubes and quantify the VOCs in the sample.

3 Submission of results

Participants shall submit their results using the reporting template in Annex 1. All reported data, remarks, and other correspondence will be kept confidential. In the report, results, selected comments, etc. will be reproduced in anonymised form. The participants will be requested to quantify, including the measurement uncertainty, the components in the sample.

The measurement report shall be sent to VSL no later than 8th December 2023.

3.1 Uncertainty requirements

The report of the participant should not only contain the measurement results, but also an estimate of the measurement uncertainty. Document EA 4/02 "Expression of the Uncertainty of Measurement in Calibration" describes the preferred method of uncertainty estimation [6].

The participants are requested to provide, a table listing the evaluated sources for uncertainty together with their calculated relative contribution to the total combined uncertainty should be presented (see, e.g., EA-4/02 for an example how to describe an uncertainty budget).

Document EA-4/02 can be downloaded from the web site of the European accreditation organisation (www.european-accreditation.org).

Other guidance documents can of course be used as well for the uncertainty evaluation. A more chemistry-related document on uncertainty calculation is published by Eurachem and CITAC. This guide CG4 "Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurements" can be downloaded from www.eurachem.org.

To enable the calculation of the zeta scores, it is necessary that the laboratory reports the uncertainty of the measurement results. For the laboratories that can't report their measurement uncertainties please provide the maximum allowed deviation (relative or absolute) from the reference value.

Uncertainty sources to consider when determining the uncertainty of the measurement results include the desorption efficiency, the uncertainty of the calibration standards and repeatability, reproducibility and drift of the analytical method. Examples of uncertainty calculations are given in Annex 5 of the project deliverable available online [2].

4 Evaluation of performance

4.1 Zeta scores (ζ)

The zeta scores for the assessment of laboratory results obtained in the framework of proficiency testing are calculated using to the equation (1) according to ISO 13528 [7].

$$\zeta_{lab(i)} = \frac{m_{lab(i)} - m_{ref(i)}}{\sqrt{u_{lab(i)}^2 + u_{ref(i)}^2}} \quad \text{eq. (1)}$$

Where:

$\zeta_{lab(i)}$ = zeta score of the participating laboratory for VOC i

$m_{lab(i)}$ = laboratory result (i.e., the laboratory mean value) for the mass of VOC i in the sorbent tube (ng).

$m_{ref(i)}$ = reference value for the mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube (ng)

$u_{lab(i)}^2$ = standard uncertainty of the result from the participant for the mass of VOC i in the sorbent tube (ng)

$u_{ref(i)}^2$ = standard uncertainty of the reference value for the mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube (ng)

The interpretation of the zeta scores is similar to that of Z-scores and is as follows:

- $|\zeta| \leq 2$ satisfactory result
- $2 < |\zeta| < 3$ questionable result
- $|\zeta| \geq 3$ unsatisfactory result

5 Report

A report will be written including:

- Description PT results.
- Results homogeneity test.
- Reference values.
- Individual results and expanded uncertainties reported by the participants.
- Rating of the laboratory performance.
- information on the repeatability and reproducibility of the data.
- an evaluation of the major uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting identified during the comparison.

In the report, the participants are identified by means of a laboratory code, which is assigned by VSL. The assigned code is only disclosed to the laboratory in question.

6 Schedule

Event	Period
Call for participants	May 2023
Closure of enrollment	August 2023
ILC protocol available	September 2023
Workshop at VITO	18 October 2023
ILC part 1 sample preparation	October 2023 *
Homogeneity study and reference value determination	October 2023
Dispatch samples to participants	1 st week November 2023 **
Final date submitting measurement report	8 th December 2023
Draft report available	March 2024
Webinar on the findings of the interlaboratory comparison	April 2024
Final report available	May 2024

*) Second half of October, after the workshop the samples will be prepared. Please make sure the sorbent tubes are provided (clean and ready for sampling) before the 16th October 2023 at VITO.

**) An update will be sent about the shipment of the samples. The shipment will be performed by an express courier, to prevent any pollution of the samples during transport.

7 Contact

7.1 VITO

Frederick Maes

VITO Health
Industriezone Vlasmee 5
2400 Mol
Belgium
+32 14 33 69 61
frederick.maes@vito.be

7.2 VSL contact details (coordinator)

VSL will determine the reference value for the ILC and process the participant data. The contact details of the experts are given below:

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Thijsseweg 11
2629 JA Delft
The Netherlands
+31 (0)6 3111 9895
idekrom@vsl.nl

Any questions, queries should be sent to the coordinator, as well as an **early notification** if the terms and conditions of participation in this comparison cannot be met.

References

1. EN 16516:2017 Construction products – Assessment of release of dangerous substances – Determination of emissions into indoor air.
2. ISO 6145-4:2004 Gas analysis – Preparation of calibration gas mixtures using dynamic volumetric methods – part 4: Continuous syringe injection method.
3. ISO 16017-1:2000 Indoor, ambient and workplace air sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by sorbent tube/thermal.desorption/capillary gas chromatograph – Part 1: Pumped sampling.
4. ISO 12963:2017 Gas analysis – Comparison methods for the determination of the composition of gas mixtures based on one- and two-point calibration.
5. BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC and OIML, 2008, Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement JCGM 100:2008, GUM 1995 with Minor Corrections (BIPM), 2020.
https://www.bipm.org/utils/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf
6. ISO 13528:2022 Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison.
7. ISO/IEC 17043:2010 Conformity assessment – General requirements for proficiency testing.

Annex A: Measurement report ILC MetrIAQ part 1

Laboratory name:

Tube numbers:

Authors:

Measurement date:

7.3 Calibration standards

Describe the calibration standards used to calibrate the instrument

7.4 Instrumentation

Describe the configuration and the parameters of the instrument used

7.5 Sample handling

Describe how the samples were handled

7.6 Calibration method and value assignment

Describe how the instrument was calibrated and how the results were calculated

7.7 Uncertainty

Describe the evaluation of measurement uncertainties

7.8 Results

Report for results

Tube number:

Component	Mass (ng)	Expanded uncertainty (ng)	Coverage factor
<i>n</i> -Hexane			
MIBK			
Toluene			
Butyl acetate			
Cyclohexanone			
<i>o</i> -Xylene			
1,3,5-trimethylbenzene			
Phenol			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			

Tube number:

Component	Mass (ng)	Expanded uncertainty (ng)	Coverage factor
<i>n</i> -Hexane			
MIBK			
Toluene			
Butyl acetate			
Cyclohexanone			
<i>o</i> -Xylene			
1,3,5-trimethylbenzene			
Phenol			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			

Tube number:

Component	Mass (ng)	Expanded uncertainty (ng)	Coverage factor
<i>n</i> -Hexane			
MIBK			
Toluene			
Butyl acetate			
Cyclohexanone			
<i>o</i> -Xylene			
1,3,5-trimethylbenzene			
Phenol			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			

Average:

Component	Mass (ng)	Expanded uncertainty (ng)	Coverage factor
<i>n</i> -Hexane			
MIBK			
Toluene			
Butyl acetate			
Cyclohexanone			
<i>o</i> -Xylene			
1,3,5-trimethylbenzene			
Phenol			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			
Non target compound			

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

Annex 3: Report on interlaboratory comparison for the analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled onto sorbent tubes

Authors: Iris de Krom¹, Wouter van der Hout¹, Adriaan van der Veen¹, Frederick Maes²

Lead partner: **VSL**¹

Other partners: VITO²

Version date: 6 June 2024

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1 Introduction

Considering that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of these emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection.

The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Within the framework of the project a interlaboratory comparison (ILC) was organised containing 2 parts:

- Part 1: Analysis of gCRMs, results in this report
- Part 2: Emission test chamber method, results in a separate report

The aim of the part 1 of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed gCRM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents relevant for emissions from building materials.

The ILC protocol describes how the ILC was performed [2]. Furthermore, information about the preparation and analysis of developed gCRMs has been reported in a project deliverable available online [3].

The evaluation of the results is performed using Zeta scores (ζ) as described in ISO 13528 [4]. The reference values were determined by VSL, by verification of the mass sampled into the sorbent tubes according to ISO 12963 [5]. For the performance rating, the reference values were used as assigned values save for n-hexane for which the consensus value was used.

2 Participants

A total of 8 labs participated in this ILC (Table 1). In this report the results of the labs are exclusively referred to by means of their anonymous lab code.

Table 1 – Participants ILC

Organisation	Country
BAM	Germany
Danish Technological Institute	Denmark
Eco-Institute	Germany
Eurofins Product Testing	Denmark
Fraunhofer WKI	Germany
Normec Product Testing	Belgium

TUBITAK	Turkey
VITO	Belgium

3 ILC samples

3.1 Participant sorbent tubes

Each participant sent VITO four clean (conditioned) ready-for-use sorbent tubes, with Tenax TA® as sorbent material. Three tubes were used for sampling with the VOC gas mixture.

3.2 Preparation and sampling

VITO prepared dynamically a calibration gas mixture containing the selected VOCs in air according to ISO 6145-4 (Table 2) [6]. The gas mixture was sampled onto sorbent tubes provided by the participants according to ISO 16017-1 [7].

Table 2 – Selected VOCs

VOC	CAS number
n-Hexane	110-54-3
Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	108-10-1
Toluene	108-88-3
Butyl acetate	123-86-4
Cyclohexanone	108-94-1
o-Xylene	95-47-6
Phenol	108-95-2
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	108-67-8

3.2.1 Preparation dynamic gas mixture

The dynamic generation of gaseous VOCs at indoor air level concentrations (and at occupational hygiene levels) in a carrier gas throughout a glass distribution line is achieved by fluid injection through a capillary according to ISO 6145-4 [6]. The fluid, a metrologically traceable solution of the VOCs, is thermally heated, evaporated and injected dynamically into the carrier gas stream.

The main components of the capillary dosage unit are the capillary (glass or a deactivated fused silica column), a pressure reducer and a stainless-steel housing. A pressure difference between both ends of the capillary forces the liquid through it. At the upper end of the capillary, the fluid is flash-heated and evaporated. The resulting vapour is dynamically injected into a primary flow of mass flow controlled nitrogen. This flow enters at the low pressure side of the capillary and transports the evaporated mixture to a Mass Flow Controller to take an aliquot and transfer it into the nitrogen carrier gas stream in the distribution line. The reservoir containing the liquid is placed on analytical balance which allows a continuous measurement of liquid consumption at any time during its injection process.

Furthermore, the stability of the generated gas mixture is measured by an online GC-FID system equipped with an injection loop and total hydrocarbon analyser.

The technique of capillary dosage is theoretically based on Poiseuille's equation which allows the calculation of a laminar flow rate through a cylindrical tube with radius r . For a pressure difference Δp over a length l , the fluid flow is calculated according to equation (1).

$$Qv = \Delta p \pi r^4 / 8 N l \quad (1)$$

where:

Δp : pressure drop across a cylindrical tube ($N\ m^{-2}$)

r : internal tube radius (m)

l : the tube length (m)

N : the dynamic viscosity ($kg\ ms^{-1}$)

Qv : the fluid flow ($m^3\ s^{-1}$).

The concentrations of the VOCs ($\mu g\ m^{-3}$) are calculated using the mass loss of the mixture in the reservoir ($\mu g\ min^{-1}$) and the different mass flow controlled nitrogen flows ($m^3\ min^{-1}$), which are all calibrated with primary flow meters and corrected to standard conditions (101.315 kPa and 293.15 K). The total gas concentration of the mixture is recalculated to the individual VOCs by using the mass fractions of each VOC in the mixture.

3.2.2 Sampling of the ILC tubes

The sorbent tubes were prepared via pumped sampling, according to ISO 16017-1, of known volumes of the gas mixture created by the capillary dosage in the glass distribution line [7]. Based on the VSL infrastructure, a sampling manifold with 6 MFC (Bronkhorst, Netherlands) in sucking mode was developed. The MFCs are connected to a vacuum pump at the back side and equipped with a 3-way valve at the front side to be able to switch between lab air and the distribution line. For TTA tubes, sampling flows of $100\ mL\ min^{-1}$ are used with a sampling period of 10 minutes.

3.2.3 Homogeneity study

For QA/QC reasons, 1 sampling train consisted of three tubes for the participating lab, 2 tubes for VSL for the determination of the reference value, and 1 tube for VITO analysis. The latter was used for a quick check by VITO using a TD-GC-MS to verify whether the loading was performed successfully. Based on these analysis (and on the GC-FID analysis by VSL, see the results in Figure 1) it was decided whether the loaded tubes could be sent out to the participants. This way, it was noticed that something went wrong with the sampling for lab 1, so these loadings were repeated more than 4 weeks after the initial loadings and have to some extent different masses.

3.3 Reference value

The reference values for the VOC masses on the tubes were determined by VSL against primary gaseous reference gas mixtures prepared. In the MetrIAQ project, a report was published on the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants [8].

For the ILC, a calibration gas mixture containing the selected VOCs in dry, clean air was prepared by VSL according to ISO 6145-4 [6]. The calibration gas mixture was sampled onto sorbent tubes according to ISO 16017-1 [7]. These were used to verify tubes sampled by VITO during the ILC to determine the reference values according to ISO 12963 [5] (Figure 1, Table 3). Based on the calibration the ILC reference value was calculated according to equation (2).

$$m_{ILC} = \frac{m_{i(dynamic)} A_{ILC}}{A_{i(dynamic)}} \quad (2)$$

Where:

m_{ILC} : mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube based on the verification (ng)

$m_{i(dynamic)}$: mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube from the dynamic gPRM used for calibration (ng)

A_{ILC} : peak area of VOC i for the ILC

$A_{i(dynamic)}$: peak area of VOC i for the dynamic gPRM

Figure 1 – Verification results, together with the ILC participant tubes 2 VSL tubes were sampled, simultaneously. The tubes were analysed by VSL to determine the reference values. The peak area of each component is shown for the 2 tubes sampled simultaneously with the participants tubes. The results of lab 1 deviate because these tubes were sampled four weeks after sampling of the other tubes. Lab 3 did not participate in the ILC, only in the workshop.

Table 3 – ILC reference values (m) and associated expanded uncertainty $U(m)$.

VOC	All participants (save lab 1)		Lab 1	
	m (ng)	$U(m)$ (ng) ($k = 2$)	m (ng)	$U(m)$ (ng) ($k = 2$)
n-Hexane	49.48*	2.47*	103.31	5.17
MIBK	118.96	5.95	127.38	6.37
Toluene	109.64	5.48	116.79	5.84
Butyl acetate	73.86	3.69	78.86	3.94
Cyclohexanone	105.83	5.29	107.96	5.40
o-Xylene	139.30	6.97	145.64	7.28
Phenol	60.76	3.04	79.93	4.00
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	119.02	5.95	123.12	6.16

* reference value not used as assigned value.

The reference values for lab 1 differ from the other labs as the tubes were sampled four weeks later. The results for all the labs, save from lab 1, are comparable within the uncertainty of 5 %. Therefore, the same reference value for each VOC is used for all the labs, save for lab 1. However, the reference value for n-hexane could not be determined as n-hexane showed instability on the VSL tubes used for the ILC (Figure 2). Over a period of 15 days the peak area decreased to half its initial value. For n-hexane a consensus value was calculated and used to rate the participants' results. After looking at the data, the n-hexane consensus value was also used for lab 1. It was not evident that the mass of n-hexane was meaningfully different for lab 1.

Figure 2 – Stability results n-hexane sampled into VSL tubes, the tubes were analysed 1, 2, 3 and 15 days after sampling on day 0.

4 Results of the participants

4.1 Participant measurement information

The participants provided information regarding the calibration standards, instrumentation, sample handling, calibration method, value assignment and uncertainty evaluation used during the ILC (Table 4).

Table 4 – Overview of calibration standards, instrumentation, sample handling, calibration method and value assignment and uncertainty evaluation of the participants

Lab	Calibration standards	Instrumentation	Sample handling	Calibration method and value assignment	Uncertainty evaluation
1	Supplier of used analytical standards: Sigma Aldrich; all of them with a purity of 99 %	TDS (TD-100 Markes): starting temperature 280°C, cooling temperature -30°C, final heating 300°C, transfer line 200°C. GC-MS (5975 Agilent): DB5 column (60m, 0,25mm, 250µm), starting temperature 32°C, end temperature 300°C, transfer line 280°C.	Tubes stored at room temperature for 3 days before analysis	Calibration and quantification with original response of external standards and also using internal standards.	Assumed uncertainty of measurement is 2,3-7,1 %, our basis is a worst case assumption of 10 %, in case of phenol even 15 %.
2	Commercial available standards from Sigma Aldrich, Merck and other manufacturers.	ATD TD100 from Markes, GCMS from Agilent, 30 m HP-5 column.	The samples were analysed on TD-GC-MS.	The results are calculated using relative response factors according to toluene.	The relative standard deviation is component dependent but for most components it is 10% whereas the expanded uncertainty is 2xRSD.
4	Self-made calibration standards solved in methanol. Lowest standard +- 2ng, highest standard +- 100ng	Agilent 7820A gas chromatograph and Markes TD-100xr thermal desorber. Desorption temperature: 300°C, Desorption flow: 25 ml/min, Desorption time: 10minutes, Cryo trap: 10°C and 320°C, Carrier gas: Helium 1.6ml/min	Tenax TA; (Markes 35/60) spiked with 25ng 2-fluortoluene	Calibration curve, Masshunter Quantitative Analysis used for calculation.	-
5	Gravimetric methanolic solutions of the 8 VOCs	Markes TD-100 desorber. Desorption temperature: 300°C / desorption flow: 30 ml/min / desorption time 10 minutes. Cold trap:	Samples were stored at room temperature under small nitrogen flow	5 points calibration curve with external calibration method	Based on the results of the method validation the measurement uncertainties were calculated according to

Lab	Calibration standards	Instrumentation	Sample handling	Calibration method and value assignment	Uncertainty evaluation
		max heating rate 10-350°C / trap heating time: 5 min Carrier gas: He / Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min Rxi-5Sil-MS 60 m x 0.25 mmID x 1.0 µ Trace GC Ultra (Thermo) / MS: DSQ II (Thermo)			ISO 20988:2007 (with reference to the GUM document, Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement) considering the bias, the repeatability and the reproducibility of the method.
6	Authentic reference standards of pure components diluted in MeOH, or authentic reference mixes. Spiked onto Tenax tubes, 1 µL.	TDX-100, Tenax tube desorption at 260 °C for 5 min. GC, Agilent 8890, Column: 5% phenyl 95% methylpolysiloxane column, 60 m x 250 µm x 0.25 µm, GC temp range: 40-300 °C, Runtime 47 min, Carrier gas: He, 1 ml/min, 15 psi. MS. Agilent 5977B, Range: 33-550 m/Z. Software MassHunter	Samples spiked with internal standard prior to shipment. Samples desorbed in Markes TDX-100 and analyzed on Agilent 5977 GC-MS	Calibrated by spiking Tenax tubes with reference mixes containing from 0.5 to 1000 ng.	The uncertainty is evaluated for: Chemicals, Liquid handling, Precision (instrument), Trueness (instrument), Accuracy (instrument). All are determined using minimum 10 measurements
7	1000 mg/kg(1000ppm) of the VOCs(n-Hexane, Methyl Isobutyl Ketone, Toluene, Butyl acetate, Cyclohexanone, o-Xylene, 1.3.5-trimethylbenzene) were prepared gravimetrically in methanol and further diluted into four concentration levels (50,100,150,200 mg/kg). Volumes of 1 µL of the VOC mixtures were spiked into the Tenax TA sorbent tubes and purged with He at a flow of 50 mL min ⁻¹ for 1 minute.	Perkin Elmer ATD TurboMatrix 350 Thermal Desorber connected to Perkin Elmer Clarus 600TGas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry. Column: TG 1MS (L = 60 m, ID = 0.25 mm, film thickness 0.25 µm, from Thermo). GC Temp Program: Temp 1: 50 °C, hold: 2 min, Rate 1: 8°C /min, Temp 2: 200°C, hold: 0 min. TD (Turbomatrix 350): Tube temp: 250 °C, Trap temp: -30 °C / 300 °C, Desorb: 5 min, Purge: 1 min, Desorb flow: 30 mL/min, Inlet split: 10 mL/min, outlet split: 20mL/min, Valve: 230 °C, Transfer Line: 220°C. The mass	1 µL of the 200 mg/kg Toluene D8 (IS) prepared in methanol was spiked into the sample tubes (Tenax TA) and purged with He at a flow of 50 mL min ⁻¹ for 1 minute. The sample tubes were placed into the TDGCMS for analysis.	Four concentration levels (50,100,150,200 mg/kg) of the VOC mixture were used for calibration. 1 µL of VOC mixture and 200 mg/kg Toluene D8 (IS) prepared in methanol were spiked into the Tenax TA sorbent tubes and purged with He at a flow of 50 mL min ⁻¹ for 1 minute. The results were calculated using four point calibration.	The relative expanded uncertainty (U) of the measurements results is estimated taking into account all the different contributions listed below. Parameters. Mass of native sample, Mass of internal standard, Native stock solution, Internal stock solution, Repeatability, Intermediate precision, Recovery, Calibration graph. The uncertainty budgets were identified based on the EURACHEM

Lab	Calibration standards	Instrumentation	Sample handling	Calibration method and value assignment	Uncertainty evaluation
		spectra data was acquired over a mass range of 50 - 300 amu.			Guide GUM (Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement).
8	Five liquid solutions were prepared, that contained all analytes in different concentration ([40, 200, 360, 520, 680] ng/ μ L). The purity of the substances is usually of analytical grade ($\geq 99\%$). One μ L of these solutions was spiked respectively onto individual thermal desorption Tenax TA tubes. Two of these sets were measured, so that two data points per concentration were available. In addition, a solution with a concentration of 100 ng/ μ L was prepared and 6 tubes were spiked with 1 μ L of this solution and were subsequently measured as well (test of repeatability & trueness).	We used a thermal desorption gas chromatography flame ionisation detector (TD-GC-FID) for analysis. The TD-GC-FID consisted of a TDSA 2 (Gerstel, Germany), a CIS 3 (Gerstel, Germany) and a 6890N (Agilent, USA). The column was an RTX-Volatiles (Restek, 60 m, 0.32 mm ID, 1.5 μ m). A constant pressure of 1.3 bar (equals about 2.5 mL/min flow) and He (99.9999%, Linde) as a carrier gas was used. The temperature programme of the TD system started at 40 $^{\circ}$ C (1 min hold) and was heated with a rate of 40 $^{\circ}$ C/min to 280 $^{\circ}$ C (5 min hold). The CIS traps the analytes at -100 $^{\circ}$ C, then, after complete desorption, heats the liner with a rate of 12 $^{\circ}$ C/s to 280 $^{\circ}$ C (3 min hold). The effluent was introduced (splitless) into the GC column and the temperature programme of the GC started: 40 $^{\circ}$ C (5 min hold), heated with a rate of 4 $^{\circ}$ C/min to 80 $^{\circ}$ C, then heated with a rate of 7 $^{\circ}$ C/min to 180 $^{\circ}$ C, and then heated with a rate of 10 $^{\circ}$ C/min to 260 $^{\circ}$ C (4 min hold). The FID was operated	The tubes were delivered and then stored for a week at room temperature. Then the three loaded tubes and one shipping blank were measured with our device (no spiking/only usual procedure).	The calibration solutions were spiked onto respective tubes and then measured with our TDGC-FID system. An external calibration curve was computed by linear regression. The area of each substance in the chromatogram was determined and then translated into a mass with help of the calibration curve. Blank values were quite low (close to zero) except for phenol, but this was due to the intercept of the phenols calibration curve. So no blank correction was performed for any substance.	Purity of substances, uncertainty of the balance, pipettes and flasks used for calibration, uncertainty of μ L-syringe for spiking, precision, trueness and accuracy of the TD-GC-FID.

Lab	Calibration standards	Instrumentation	Sample handling	Calibration method and value assignment	Uncertainty evaluation
		at a temperature of 280 °C, with a flow of 35 mL/min H ₂ , 350 mL/min air and 42.5 mL/min He make up gas.			
9	A certified calibration standard 100 ng/μl and a dilution 10 ng/μl were used for system calibration	Shimadzu TD-30R and GC/MS AQ-2020	Sample were spiked with IStd d8-Toluene. Desorption on TD-30R with 250 °C and 60 ml/min He for 5 min	Five-point calibration 10, 25, 50, 100 and 250 ng and IStd d8-Toluene	For estimation of uncertainty Nordtest-calculation was used. Extended uncertainty with k=2 (95%) is 41.7%.

The labs used commercially available calibration standards or prepared their own calibration standards. TD-GC-MS or -FID systems were used to analyse the samples. In general the samples were stored at room temperature for several days before analysis. Multi calibration standards were used by the labs to obtain a multipoint calibration. The uncertainty evaluation was performed in various ways by the labs.

4.2 Evaluation of the results

The zeta scores for the assessment of laboratory results obtained in the framework of proficiency testing are calculated using to the equation (3) according to ISO 13528 [4].

$$\zeta_{lab(i)} = \frac{m_{lab(i)} - m_{ref(i)}}{\sqrt{u_{lab(i)}^2 + u_{ref(i)}^2}} \quad \text{eq. (3)}$$

Where:

$\zeta_{lab(i)}$: zeta score of the participating laboratory for VOC i

$m_{lab(i)}$: laboratory result (i.e., the laboratory mean value) for the mass of VOC i in the sorbent tube (ng).

$m_{ref(i)}$: reference value for the mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube (ng)

$u_{lab(i)}^2$: standard uncertainty of the result from the participant for the mass of VOC i in the sorbent tube (ng)

$u_{ref(i)}^2$: standard uncertainty of the reference value for the mass of VOC i sampled into the sorbent tube (ng)

The interpretation of the zeta scores is similar to that of Z -scores and is as follows [4]:

$ \zeta \leq 2.0$	satisfactory result
$2.0 < \zeta < 3.0$	questionable result
$ \zeta \geq 3.0$	unsatisfactory result

4.3 Consensus values

For *n*-hexane instead of a reference value a consensus value from participant results was used. The consensus value was calculated using the reported data from all participants (Table 5). A random effects model was used, which was fitted using restricted maximum likelihood [9-11]. An uncertainty component (τ) was included to account for the fact that not all results were mutually consistent within the stated expanded uncertainties.

Table 5 – Consensus values (m), associated standard uncertainties ($u(m)$) and the excess standard deviation (τ) for the masses (ng)

Component	m	$u(m)$	τ
<i>n</i> -Hexane	101.411	6.214	0.001
MIBK	118.516	6.259	7.240
Toluene	114.045	6.795	10.342
Butyl acetate	78.093	3.630	0.000
Cyclohexanone	102.271	5.639	0.000
<i>o</i> -Xylene	142.483	6.306	0.000
Phenol	50.760	6.625	12.316
1,3,5-trimethylbenzene	108.365	3.974	0.000

The consensus values were calculated from the complete data sets. Notwithstanding that one laboratory (lab 1) received tubes with different masses, no correction was applied in the case of *n*-hexane, for the reference values were deemed unfit for making such correction. From the reported data, it was not evident that the mass *n*-hexane differed much from the other laboratories. For the other components, a correction to the result of lab 1 was applied before fitting the data to obtain the consensus value.

The values for the excess standard deviation τ indicate that there are substantial differences between the reported results. None of the data sets (see also section 4.4) is mutually consistent.

4.4 Evaluation Laboratory results

The reported results for the mass *n*-hexane are shown in Figure 3 and the zeta scores in Figure 4.

Figure 3 – Reported data for the mass *n*-hexane

Figure 4 – Zeta scores for the mass *n*-hexane

The reported results for the mass MIBK are shown in Figure 5 and the zeta scores in Figure 6.

Figure 5 – Reported data for the mass MIBK

Figure 6 – Zeta scores for the mass MIBK

The reported results for the mass toluene are shown in Figure 7 and the zeta scores in Figure 8.

Figure 7 – Reported data for the mass toluene

Figure 8 – Zeta scores for the mass toluene

The reported results for the mass butyl acetate are shown in Figure 9 and the zeta scores in Figure 10.

Figure 9 – Reported results for the mass butyl acetate

Figure 10 – Zeta scores for the mass butyl acetate

The reported results for the mass cyclohexanone are shown in Figure 11 and the zeta scores in Figure 12.

Figure 11 – Reported data for the mass cyclohexanone

Figure 121 – Zeta scores for the mass cyclohexanone

The reported results for the mass *o*-xylene are shown in Figure 13 and the zeta scores in Figure 14.

Figure 13 – Reported data for the mass *o*-xylene

Figure 14 – Zeta scores for the mass *o*-xylene

The reported results for the mass phenol are shown in Figure 15 and the zeta scores in Figure 16.

Figure 15 – Reported data for the mass phenol

Figure 16 – Zeta scores for the mass phenol

The reported results for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene are shown in Figure 17 and the zeta scores in Figure 18.

Reported data for 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

Figure 17 – Reported data for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

Zeta scores for 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

Figure 18 – Zeta scores for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

5 Conclusion

The MetrIAQ ILC was carried out to assess the participants capabilities in measuring VOCs, relevant in emissions from building materials, in sorbent tubes. These results highlight the complexity of these measurements, both for the providers and the participants. The results from the labs indicate that lab 9 performed satisfactory for all VOCs, the other labs that perform satisfactory for most VOCs and questionable for a few components. The biased results imply that the participants uncertainty evaluation does not include all significant sources of uncertainty.

References

1. EN 16516:2017: Construction products – Assessment of release of dangerous substances – Determination of emissions into indoor air.
2. I. de Krom, W. van der Hout, A.M.H. van der Veen, F. Maes, protocol for the interlaboratory comparison for the analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled into sorbent tubes, 2023.
3. I. de Krom, E. Henderson, A.M.H. van der Veen, A. Baldan, F. Maes, Guideline for the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants stated in the EU-LCI list with relative uncertainties below 5 % ($k = 2$) and a shelf life of at least 1 year, 2023, [20NRM04-MetrIAQ A1.3.5 VSL Deliverable-report-D3 Final.pdf](#)
4. ISO 13528:2022: Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison.
5. ISO 12963:2017: Gas analysis – Comparison methods for the determination of the composition of gas mixtures based on one- and two-point calibration.
6. ISO 6145-4:2004: Gas analysis – Preparation of calibration gas mixtures using dynamic volumetric methods – part 4: Continuous syringe injection method.
7. ISO 16017-1:2000: Indoor, ambient and workplace air sampling and analysis of volatile organic compounds by sorbent tube/thermal desorption/capillary gas chromatograph – Part 1: Pumped sampling.
8. I. de Krom, W. van der Hout, A. van der Veen, F. Maes, Report workshop sampling and analysis of certified reference gas standards sampled onto sorbent tubes, 2024
9. Viechtbauer, W. (2010). Conducting meta-analyses in R with the metafor package. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 36(3), 1-48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v036.i03>
10. Viechtbauer, W. (2005). Bias and efficiency of meta-analytic variance estimators in the random-effects model. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 30(3), 261–293. <https://doi.org/10.3102/10769986030003261>
11. Raudenbush, S. W. (2009). Analyzing effect sizes: Random effects models. In H. Cooper, L. V. Hedges, & J. C. Valentine (Eds.), *The handbook of research synthesis and meta-analysis* (2nd ed., pp. 295–315). New York: Russell Sage Foundation.

Annex A: laboratory results and evaluation

Table 6 – Reported results for the mass n-hexane, the consensus value was used for the calculations save for lab 1 where the reference value was used

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	102.00	10.00	97.532	6.078	0.074
2	95.00	18.00	97.532	6.078	-0.565
4	440.00	145.20	97.532	6.078	4.647
5	88.00	12.00	97.532	6.078	-1.047
6	193.00	39.00	97.532	6.078	4.475
7	88.46	14.70	97.532	6.078	-1.346
8	131.00	26.00	97.532	6.078	2.054
9	120.00	50.00	97.532	6.078	0.722

Table 7 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass MIBK

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	131.00	13.00	127.378	6.369	0.500
2	99.90	10.00	118.958	5.948	-1.828
4	172.00	56.76	118.958	5.948	1.859
5	101.00	6.00	118.958	5.948	-1.733
6	151.00	30.00	118.958	5.948	2.095
7	96.71	17.78	118.958	5.948	-2.373
8	133.00	13.00	118.958	5.948	1.964
9	125.00	53.00	118.958	5.948	0.227

Table 8 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass toluene

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	134.00	13.00	116.789	5.839	2.415
2	100.00	8.00	109.641	5.482	-0.930
4	165.00	54.45	109.641	5.482	2.023
5	93.00	6.00	109.641	5.482	-1.634
6	135.00	27.00	109.641	5.482	1.841
7	97.62	14.58	109.641	5.482	-1.543
8	124.80	12.00	109.641	5.482	2.298
9	113.00	47.00	109.641	5.482	0.142

Table 9 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass butyl acetate

Lab	Value(ng)	U(ng)	Ref(ng)	Ref.U(ng)	zeta
1	79.00	8.0	78.857	3.943	0.032
2	57.00	7.5	73.860	3.693	-2.814
4	120.00	39.6	73.860	3.693	2.320
5	67.00	5.0	73.860	3.693	0.891
6	104.00	21.0	73.860	3.693	2.827
7	82.76	13.77	73.860	3.693	1.249
8	82.60	8.0	73.860	3.693	1.984
9	76.00	32.0	73.860	3.693	0.133

Table 10 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass cyclohexanone

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	109.0	11.00	107.964	5.398	0.169
2	93.9	9.40	105.828	5.291	-1.223
4	120.0	39.60	105.828	5.291	0.709
5	89.0	9.00	105.828	5.291	-0.146
6	120.0	24.00	105.828	5.291	1.153
7	95.1	14.24	105.828	5.291	-1.412
8	150.9	15.00	105.828	5.291	-0.331
9	104.0	43.00	105.828	5.291	-0.084

Table 11 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass o-xylene

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	145.00	15.00	145.637	7.282	-0.076
2	121.00	12.00	139.303	6.965	-1.454
4	194.00	64.02	139.303	6.965	1.699
5	125.00	9.00	139.303	6.965	1.099
6	151.00	30.00	139.303	6.965	0.760
7	119.69	18.68	139.303	6.965	-1.968
8	102.40	10.00	139.303	6.965	1.402
9	131.00	55.00	139.303	6.965	-0.300

Table 12 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass phenol

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	59.0	9.00	79.934	3.997	-4.252
2	27.0	6.30	60.761	3.038	-9.654
4	66.0	21.78	60.761	3.038	0.476
5	53.0	4.00	60.761	3.038	-2.692
6	53.0	11.00	60.761	3.038	-1.360
7	-	-	-	-	-
8	76.3	15.00	60.761	3.038	0.998
9	63.0	27.00	60.761	3.038	0.165

Table 13 – Reported results, reference values and zeta-scores for the mass 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene

Lab	<i>m</i> (ng)	<i>U</i> (ng)	<i>m</i> _{ref} (ng)	<i>U</i> (<i>m</i> _{ref}) (ng)	zeta
1	108.00	11.00	123.123	6.156	-2.400
2	91.30	12.00	119.017	5.951	-2.886
4	162.00	53.46	119.017	5.951	1.598
5	92.00	5.00	119.017	5.951	-3.350
6	114.00	23.00	119.017	5.951	-0.422
7	102.06	16.87	119.017	5.951	-1.896
8	131.40	13.00	119.017	5.951	1.732
9	122.00	51.00	119.017	5.951	0.116

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

Annex 4: Protocol for the inter-laboratory comparison for the measurement of emission reference materials (ERM)

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1 Introduction

Given that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products, into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of the emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection. The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Two different approaches were used for the synthesis of ERM: the impregnation of porous materials (activated carbons, zeolites etc.) with VOC, and the encapsulation of VOC inside of a polymeric material (μ -capsules).

Within the framework of the project this interlaboratory comparison (ILC) is organised containing two parts:

- Part 1: Analysis of gCRMs, which took place in October 2023
- Part 2: Emission test chamber method, described in this protocol

The aim of part 2 of the ILC is 1) to validate the developed ERM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to determine emissions of VOCs from building materials that relevant for their evaluation.

2 Samples

2.1 Preparation

Project partners BAM and IMM will prepare emission reference materials containing selected VOCs (**Table 1**). The participants will receive a package with four materials. The materials should be placed in an emission test chamber within a few days after arrival. The emission must be tested according to EN 16516. The testing must include values of day 3, 7 and 14 after loading. Recommendations for the sampling are given further below.

Table 1. Selected VOCs.

VOC	CAS number
<i>n</i> -hexane	110-54-3
toluene	108-88-3
D-limonene	5989-27-5
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	104-76-7

The concentration per VOC in the chamber air is expected to be in the range of 20–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ after 14 days.

2.2 Storage stability

An internal validation of the ERMs was conducted prior to part 2 of the ILC. The materials were put into sealed containers and stored for different times and under different temperatures. No influence of storage time or temperature was seen during the first six months of storage. The homogeneity and repeatability (standard deviation of the emission rate = 1–7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$) were proven to be very good.

2.3 Reference value

The reference value will be calculated as the mean value based on the information provided by the participants. Further information is given in **chapter 4**.

2.4 Sample handling and emission testing

After arrival, the materials can be stored at room temperature for a couple of days, if necessary. For testing, the materials must be unpacked. The powder material delivered in glass vials must be put completely into the provided petri dishes. The other material (pre-conditioned encapsulated VOC) is already applied in a glass petri dish and can be used as it is. The petri dishes are then to be placed into the emission test chamber (please remember to remove the lids of the petri dishes before). The emission test chamber should be operated according to EN 16516 (23 °C, 50 % relative humidity, air exchange rate of 0.5 h^{-1}). The sampling is also supposed to be performed in accordance with the standard.

Recommendations for sampling:

The sampling must be conducted exactly 3, 7 and 14 days after loading the chamber and should include at least two samplings with different volumes (e.g., 1 L and 2 L). A sampling flow of 100–200 mL/min is recommended.

3 Submission of results

Participants must submit their results using the reporting template (attached excel document). All reported data, remarks, and other correspondence will be kept confidential. In the report, results, selected comments, etc. will be reproduced in coded form. The participants will be requested to quantify the components in the chamber air as well as the measurement uncertainty.

The report shall be sent to BAM (info@metriaq.eu).

3.1 Statement of uncertainty

In order to be able to better assess an analysis result, it is necessary to specify the measurement uncertainty. Document EA 4/02 “Expression of the Uncertainty of Measurement in Calibration” describes the preferred method of uncertainty estimation [2]. Following this document, a table of the most important sources for uncertainty together with their calculated relative contribution to the total combined uncertainty should be presented.

Document EA-4/02 can be downloaded from the website of the European accreditation organisation (www.european-accreditation.org).

A more chemistry related document on uncertainty calculation is published by Eurachem and CITAC. This guide CG4 “Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurements” can be downloaded from www.eurachem.org.

Uncertainty sources to consider when determining the uncertainty of the measurement results are the uncertainty of the calibration standards and repeatability, reproducibility, drift of the analytical method, uncertainty of the sampling volume, and of the chamber parameters (humidity, air exchange rate and temperature). Examples of uncertainty calculations are given in Annex 5 of the project deliverable 3 available online [3].

The participants are encouraged to make a statement of measurement uncertainty in the results report.

4 Evaluation of performance

4.1 Reference value

The reported concentration values of the participants will be transformed into its respective emission rate (ER) by using equation (1).

$$ER_{lab(i,t)} = \frac{c_{lab(i,t)} * flow\ rate_{lab(i)}}{inweight\ ERM_{lab(i)}} \quad \text{eq. (1)}$$

Where:

$c_{lab(i,t)}$ = concentration of VOC i at sampling day t .

$ER_{lab(i,t)}$ = laboratory results (i.e., the laboratory mean value) for the emission rate (ER) of VOC i in the chamber at sampling day t .

4.2 z scores

The z scores for the assessment of laboratory results obtained in the framework of proficiency testing are calculated using to the equation (2) according to ISO 13528 [4].

$$Z_{lab(i,t=14)} = \frac{ER_{lab(i,t=14)} - ER_{ref(i,t=14)}}{S_{ref(i,t=14)}} \quad \text{eq. (2)}$$

Where:

$z_{lab(i,t=1)}$ = z score of the participating laboratory for VOC i at sampling day 14.

$ER_{lab(i,t=14)}$ = laboratory results (i.e., the laboratory mean value) for the emission rate (ER) of VOC i in the chamber at sampling day 14.

$ER_{ref(i,t=14)}$ = reference value for the emission rate (ER) of VOC i in the chamber at sampling day 14.

$s_{ref(i,t=1)}$ = standard deviation of the reference value for the emission rate (ER) of VOC i in the chamber at sampling day 14.

ISO/IEC 17043 [5] proposes the interpretation of the z score as follows:

$|z| \leq 2$ satisfactory result

$2 < |z| < 3$ questionable result

$|z| \geq 3$ unsatisfactory result

5 Report

A report will be written including:

- Description PT results.
- Results homogeneity test.
- Reference values.
- Individual results and expanded uncertainties reported by the participants.
- Rating of the laboratory performance.
- information on the repeatability and reproducibility of the data.
- an evaluation of the major uncertainty sources in sampling, analysis and reporting identified during the comparison.

In the report, the participants are identified by means of a laboratory code, which is assigned by BAM. The assigned code is kept confidential.

6 Schedule

Event	Period
Closure of enrollment	22 th December 2023
ILC protocol available	November 2023
ILC part 2 sample preparation	December 2023
Dispatch samples to participants	1 st week of January 2024 *
Final date submitting measurement report	5 th February 2024
Draft report available	March 2024
Webinar on the findings of the ILC	April 2024
Final report available	May 2024

*) An update will be sent out about the shipment of the samples. The shipment will be performed by an express courier, to prevent any pollution of the samples during transport.

7 Contact

7.1 BAM

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For more information, please visit:

<https://www.bam.de/Content/EN/Projects/MetrIAQ/metriag.html>

References

1. EN 16516:2017: Construction products – Assessment of release of dangerous substances – Determination of emissions into indoor air.
2. BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC and OIML, 2008, Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement JCGM 100:2008, GUM 1995 with Minor Corrections (BIPM), 2020.
https://www.bipm.org/utils/common/documents/jcgm/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf
3. D3 report: https://www.vsl.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/20NRM04-MetrIAQ_A1.3.5_VSL_Deliverable-report-D3_Final.pdf
4. ISO 13528:2022: Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison.
5. ISO/IEC 17043:2010 Conformity assessment – General requirements for proficiency testing.

Annex 4.2: Measurement protocol

Measurement report MetriAQ ILC part 2

Laboratory Name:

Authors:

Date of ERM delivery:

Date of chamber loading:

Component	concentration c [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]						Comment
	day 3 / V1	day 3 / V2	day 7 / V1	day 7 / V2	day 14 / V1	day 14 / V2	
n-hexane							
toluene							
D-limonene							
2-ethyl-1-hexanol							
non-target compound							
non-target compound							
non-target compound							
non-target compound							

- Calibration standards:** Describe the calibration standards used to calibrate the instrument (e.g. liquid/gaseous solution injected, how many data points?)
- Instrumentation:** Describe the configuration and the parameters of the instrument used
- Sampling:** Describe how you conducted the sampling (e.g. which volumes did you take, did you use a pump and/or a mass flow meter?)
- Calibration method and value assignment:** internal/external calibration, direct or indirect quantification, blank correction?
- Uncertainty:** Describe the evaluation of measurement uncertainties
- Results:** If results for non-target compounds are obtained these may also be reported in the table above

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

Annex 5: Report on the inter-laboratory comparison (ILC part 2) for the measurement of emission reference materials (ERM)

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Summary

This is a report about the evaluation of results obtained from inter-laboratory comparison of emission reference materials (ERMs, ILC part 2) developed in the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project *Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air* (20NRM04 MetrIAQ).

The goal for the development of ERMs is to obtain a reference material with a stable emission with a deviation of $\leq 10\%$ over at least 14 days. Two different approaches were used for the generation of ERMs: the impregnation of porous materials with selected VOCs, and the encapsulation of VOCs by polymerisation (μ -capsules). Four VOCs (*n*-hexane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene) were used for the generation of ERMs. The ERMs were validated in an internal validation and with help of the ILC part 2. Results of the internal validation are shown briefly, and results from the ILC part 2 are discussed in-depth within this report. During the ILC part 2, the toluene impregnated sample showed very good results (i.e., a reasonable emission rate, and low variability of only 18 %). Materials impregnated with *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol showed low emission rates and high variabilities (57 % and 66 % respectively). The results of μ -capsules loaded with D-limonene could not be interpreted. The emission was very low and thus often below the calibrated range of most participants. An explanation was not yet found for this behaviour.

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1 Introduction

Considering that European citizens spend more than 80 % of their time indoors, it is vital to have a healthy indoor environment. To achieve this, the release of harmful substances from building materials, such as paints, flooring, and from other products into the indoor air must be minimised. Reliable, accurate and traceable measurements of these emissions are paramount to reach high level consumer protection.

The overall aim of the MetrIAQ project (*Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air*) is to develop traceable measurement of emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from such materials by providing well-defined emission reference materials (ERM) and certified reference gas standards (gCRM), in accordance with the emission test chamber procedure described in EN 16516 [1].

Within the framework of the project an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) was organised containing 2 parts:

- Part 1: Analysis of gCRMs, results in this report
- Part 2: Emission test chamber method, results in a separate report

The aim of **part 1** of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed gCRM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents relevant for emissions from building materials. The ILC protocol describes how the ILC was performed (Annex 1 of the D5 summary report). Furthermore, information about the preparation and analysis of developed gCRMs has been reported in a project deliverable available online [2].

The evaluation of the results is performed using Zeta scores (ζ) as described in ISO 13528 [3]. The reference values were determined by VSL by verification of the mass sampled into the sorbent tubes according to ISO 12963 [4]. For the performance rating, the reference values were used as assigned values save for n-hexane for which the consensus value was used.

The aim of **part 2** of the ILC was 1) to validate the developed ERM and 2) to assess the capability of laboratories to measure VOC contents released from materials in the emission test chamber procedure. The ERMs are either impregnated porous materials produced by BAM, or μ -capsules filled with VOC produced by FhG. Four VOCs (*n*-hexane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene) were used to produce the ERMs. The goal for the ERMs is to achieve a constant VOC emission with a deviation of ≤ 10 % over at least 14 days. The ERMs were also tested in an internal validation.

2 Participants

A total of 8 labs participated in the ILC part 1 and in the ILC part 2 respectively (**Table 1**). In this report the results of the labs are exclusively referred to by means of their anonymous lab code.

Table 1. Participants of the ILCs.

Organisation	Country	Participation
BAM	Germany	Part 1 / 2
Danish Technological Institute	Denmark	Part 1 / 2
Eco-Institute	Germany	Part 1 / 2
Eurofins Product Testing	Denmark	Part 1 / 2
Fraunhofer WKI	Germany	Part 1 / 2
Knauf Gips KG	Germany	Part 2
Normec Product Testing	Belgium	Part 1
Olfasense GmbH	Germany	Part 2
PPG Amsterdam	Netherlands	Part 2
TUBITAK	Turkey	Part 1
VITO	Belgium	Part 1

3 Materials

3.1 Chemicals

All chemicals used by BAM (**Table 2**) and FhG (**Table 3**) were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification. The used porous materials were activated carbons (AC) C 40/4 and C 45/4 (CarboTech, Germany), and the non-hygroscopic zeolite BEA (Clariant). For the internal validation, AC 40-4 and 45-4 were used as received (granulates). For the ILC part 2, AC 40-4 and 45-4 were ground into powders prior to impregnation with VOC, and BEA was used as received (powder).

Table 2. Chemicals used by BAM.

Chemical [CAS]	Supplier	Purity [%]
<i>n</i> -hexane [110-54-3]	Merck	≥ 99
toluene [108-88-3]	J.T. Baker	≥ 99.5
2-ethyl-1-hexanol [104-76-7]	Fluka	99.6
D-limonene [5989-27-5]	Aldrich	97

Table 3. Chemicals used by FhG for the generation of ERMs (μ -capsules).

Chemical [CAS]	Supplier	Purity [%]
D-limonene [5989-27-5]	Thermoscientific	96
1,6-hexanediamine (HMDA) [124-09-4]	Merck	98
tolylene 2,4-diisocyanate (TDI) [584-84-9]	Sigma-Aldrich	95
TUBASSIST®FIX 157W (Tub)	CHT R. BEITLICH GmbH	
polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) M_w 31000 g/mol [9002-89-5]	Sigma Aldrich	≥ 99.5
sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) [151-21-3]	Acros organics	98
Ultra-pure water	Thermo Scientific	

4 Methods

4.1 Generation of impregnated porous materials

The impregnation of porous materials for the generation of emission reference materials (ERMs) is conducted in an autoclave. A portion of porous material and liquid VOC are placed inside the metal vessel, which is then sealed. Gaseous CO₂ is introduced until a certain pressure is reached. The autoclave is then heated to 32 °C – due to the increase in temperature, the pressure rises accordingly to about 74 bar. At these conditions, CO₂ is in its supercritical state and acts as a solvent for the VOC. The mixture inside the autoclave is stirred and the porous material is treated for a few minutes. Then the pressure and/or temperature is slowly reduced. The impregnated material can be removed from the autoclave and transferred into an emission test chamber for testing. ERMs in the form of impregnated porous materials were provided as powders. They were transported in air-tight containers.

4.2 Generation of μ -capsules

The VOC loaded capsules were prepared by a polyaddition/polycondensation reaction performed at the oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion droplet's interface. The process is schematically shown in **Figure 1**. The droplets were generated using Shirasu porous glass (SPG) membrane emulsification module (External Pressure Micro Kit (MG-20), SPG Technology Co. Ltd, Japan). The hydrophilic SPG membrane with the pore size of 9.9 μm was used for the emulsification. The final average size of capsules was 60 $\mu\text{m} \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$ and the shell thickness was about 0.9 μm . The dispersed phase, consisting of 4.03 g limonene, 0.334 g TDI and 0.167 g Tub was pressed through the membrane using nitrogen pressure. The droplets were formed at the pore openings on the surface of the membrane that was in contact with the continuous phase. The continuous phase consists of 120 ml surfactant(s) aqueous solution (1.2 g of PVA and 0.24 g of SDS). After all

organic phase was dispersed, the emulsion was placed in a heated oil bath at 40 °C and 5.5 ml of 6.25 wt% HMDA aqueous solution was added dropwise. A reaction proceeded overnight under magnetic stirring at 300 rpm and polymerisation occurs at the droplets' interface, resulting in a μ -capsule filled with VOC. After synthesis the capsules were washed three times with ultra-pure water to remove the excess of surfactants. Afterwards, a defined amount of the aqueous μ -capsule suspension was put into glass petri dishes and subsequently pre-aged. After complete water evaporation, a ready-to-use ERM is obtained. These ready-to-use petri dishes were distributed in air-tight packages.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of VOC encapsulation through interfacial polyaddition/polycondensation reaction.

4.3 Inter-laboratory comparison procedures

4.3.1 ILC part 2 protocol

Each participant received an air-tight package and a protocol with instructions. The package contained three glass vials with impregnated porous materials and a smaller air-tight package containing one or several glass petri dishes filled with μ -capsules (**Figure 2**). The number of glass petri dishes filled with μ -capsules and the amounts of impregnated powders were adjusted to the chamber sizes of the participants (**Annex 5.1**).

The participants were instructed to start the emission testing within a few days after arrival of the samples and the testing must be conducted according to EN 16516. The package is allowed to reach room temperature, it is opened and the materials from the glass vials must be completely transferred into individual petri

dishes, that were also provided with the package. The impregnated powder is supposed to be put into the bigger part of the petri dish and the smaller part of the petri dish should be used to carefully flatten the surface of the powder (without applying too much pressure). The smaller air-tight package is opened as well. The lid(s) of the ready-to-use petri dish(es) containing the μ -capsules were removed, and all petri dishes were placed into the emission test chamber.

Figure 2. Examples of a μ -capsule sample (A) and impregnated porous materials: BEA zeolite (B) and C 40/4 (C). A typical air-tight package (E) is depicted. The μ -capsule sample was packed into an additional air-tight package inside of the bigger package.

The ERMs emit *n*-hexane, toluene, D-limonene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol with a VOC specific target concentration of 20–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The testing must include values of exactly 72 h, 168 h and 336 h after loading the emission test chamber and should include at least two samplings with different volumes (e.g., 1 L and 2 L). A sampling flow of 100–200 mL/min was recommended. A measurement protocol was sent to the participants asking for the measurement results and additional information.

It was further stated in the protocol, how the results will be processed and evaluated. The analysis yields VOC specific masses of the analysed thermal desorption tube (m_{VOC}). This VOC specific mass is divided by the respective sampling volume (V_{sampling}), resulting in a VOC specific concentration (c_{VOC}). Due to the use of many different chamber sizes, the concentration is further processed into the VOC specific emission rate (ER ; **Equation 1**).

$$ER_{\text{VOC}} \left[\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{h} \times \text{g}} \right] = \frac{c_{\text{VOC}} \left[\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{m}^3} \right] \times \text{air exchange rate} \left[\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{h}} \right]}{m_{\text{ERM}} [\text{g}]} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

The evaluation of performance was supposed to be based on the z score (according to ISO 13528 [3]). The reference value ($ER_{ref, VOC, day 14}$) can be pre-determined or assigned during the inter-laboratory comparison. It can be calculated as the mean value of the reported values of all participants or of only a group of participants (e.g., experienced laboratories). The z score of a laboratory ($Z_{lab, VOC}$) is calculated as the difference of the laboratory's value and the reference value, divided by the standard deviation of the reference (**Equation 2**).

$$Z_{lab, VOC, day 14} = \frac{ER_{lab, VOC, day 14} - ER_{ref, VOC, day 14}}{S_{ref, VOC, day 14}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

ISO/IEC 17043 [5] proposes the interpretation of the z score as follows:

$ z \leq 2$	satisfactory result
$2 < z < 3$	questionable result
$ z \geq 3$	unsatisfactory result

Analytical methods of ILC part 2 participants

In this chapter we try to generalise the sampling and analytical methods used by the participants of ILC part 2. For this purpose, we asked the participants for information about their analytical system, calibration procedure, sampling and their estimated measurement uncertainty. The replies did not always include every piece of information. Especially information about the estimated measurement uncertainty differs in quantity and quality. Nonetheless, some generalisation can be done:

Almost all participants (with one exception, who used TD-GC-FID) used TD-GC-MS systems for analysis. Most devices were calibrated with five different calibration solutions spiked into Tenax tubes. The solutions are often prepared in-house. At least one participant used a certified calibration standard (100 ng/ μ L) and a dilution of this standard (10 ng/ μ L) for calibration. The calibrated concentrations and the procedure (internally or externally calibrated) differ as well. Some participants calibrated five points between 1 (or 5)–200 ng/ μ L, others between 10 (or 20)–420 ng/ μ L. At least one participant used relative response factors against the response of toluene. The calibration standards were either measured once, twice or three times. It was not always stated, but it can be assumed, that most participants must use a split for the effluent let into the GC column. The typical GC column used is an HP-5 (or comparable column, such as DB-5, VF-5 etc.) with either 30 m or 60 m in length and mainly 0.25 mm ID and 0.25 mm film thickness.

A typical temperature programme of the TD and GC will not be given here as it is too complex. Good/typical examples can be found in the literature. One participant

reported overlapping peaks of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene. This can happen with certain substances on an HP-5 (or similar) column. But in this case, it should not be a problem since the used TD-GC-MS can easily differentiate the two substances.

Most participants used a mass flow controller or a mass flow meter either integrated into the sampling pump or externally in conjunction with a sampling pump. The used sampling volumes were mainly 1 L and 2 L, a few participants used higher volumes such as 1 L and 4 L, or 2 L and 5 L (or similar).

5 Uncertainty

5.1 Uncertainty of the emission test chamber procedure (ILC part 2)

As mentioned above, replies to the request on information about the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty were not consistent. Most participants reported only the worst uncertainty, only a few differentiated between measurement uncertainty (of analysis) and the overall procedure and/or the dependence on the substance. Three participants reported parts of their uncertainty assessment. Two participants did not report a value at all, while one participant reported a very low (i.e., unreasonable low) value for a worst-case scenario of the overall procedure. This is probably due to the complexity of this topic and an oversimplified request in the questionnaire (i.e., "Describe the evaluation of measurement uncertainties"). The measurement uncertainty is highly dependent on the substance and its concentration. Thus, it should be provided for every measurement result. It seems, more knowledge and awareness should be spread about this topic in general, and more clear instructions could help the participants in their assessment.

In this chapter, we want to list and roughly sort different sources of uncertainty. An assessment of the measurement uncertainty of two substances (best-case and worst-case scenario) will be given in the upcoming deliverable report D6 of this project. The overall emission test chamber procedure consists of several parts: the operation of the emission test chamber, the air sampling, the analysis, and "others". The sampling has the lowest impact of these three. When mass flow controllers/meters are used, the relative standard deviation is usually < 5 %.

The uncertainties of analysis and of the emission test chamber can be comparable, when challenging substances are tested and analysed. In case of less challenging substances, the uncertainty of analysis should be smaller than that of the emission test chamber. The analysis can be further divided into the actual TD-GC-MS measurement, the calibration and spiking (i.e., when using an internal standard). These can be divided into even smaller parts. For example, the calibration is conducted with help of chemicals, pipettes, volumetric flasks, and a syringe for spiking the TD tubes. Each chemical and device has its own small uncertainty, which add up to the uncertainty of the calibration. The spiking (for spiking the TD tubes during calibration or to spike internal standards) is often conducted by an

automated, highly precise device with a microliter syringe and thus has only little impact. The uncertainty of the measurement device depends highly on the used type of device and its maintenance. Quality control can significantly improve the precision and accuracy of the measurement device.

The uncertainty of the emission test chamber is probably the highest. Many different parameters need to be controlled by the chamber. Some typical parameters and their tolerances described in EN 16516 concern the temperature (23 ± 1 °C), relative humidity (rel. H.; 50 ± 5 %), air exchange rate ($0.5 \text{ h}^{-1} \pm 5$ %), air flow above the sample (0.1–0.3 m/s), loading factor and more. The chamber size can differ vastly and at least one critical parameter, the air pressure, is not mentioned. Effects, such as condensation on the chamber walls can take place. Even when only focusing on the valid tolerances, it can be imagined, that high variabilities are obtained.

The category “others” includes sample handling and reporting. Gross mistakes, such as spillage of a reference material during chamber loading or reporting invalid values, can lead to deviations.

There are two main approaches for the assessment of uncertainty: the bottom-up and the top-down approach [6]. They can be used independently or in combination. The bottom-up approach tries to gather all uncertainty sources and adds up their contributions, while the top-down approach tries to find the uncertainty of the overall procedure or (bigger) segments of the procedure by many analyses of a reference (i.e., quality control standard, reference material or similar). Both approaches are useful and can be used complementary to back up each other.

6 Storage and stability of the reference materials

6.1 Storage and stability of emission reference materials

Data from the development and internal validation were used to determine repeatability, reproducibility, and storage stability of the ERMs. The data from the internal validation is found in the annex of the ERM guideline (deliverable report D2 of this project). It is presented in brief here as well to better understand the behaviour of the materials.

During the internal validation, six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel at BAM. The results are correlated in a sense that many usually variable parameters were basically the same (such as air pressure, performance of the measurement device, temperature in the laboratory etc.). This reduces the variability of the results to only a few remaining parameters, such as the homogeneity of the materials (**Table 4**). Very good homogeneities were found for the toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -

capsule sample. Mediocre homogeneities were found for the *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples.

Table 4. Results of the in-batch repeatability test. Six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel. The toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample are highly homogenous. The *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples revealed only mediocre homogeneities.

	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonene
mean ER [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]	24.0	36.2	28.2	13.1
SD [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]	3.5	1.1	5.3	0.9
relative SD [%]	14.5	3.0	18.6	6.7

Furthermore, a short and long-term stability (and indirectly a reproducibility) study was conducted with the same materials. Air-tight packages were distributed to the project partners Eurofins and BAM and stored for different times and at different temperatures. No trend was found for any of the storage conditions. High and low values were obtained for short and long storage times (0, 0.5, 1, 3, and 6 months), as well as for every temperature (-18, 5, 23 and 35 °C) (**Figure 3**). It can be concluded that the materials are insensitive to the tested storage conditions.

Figure 3. VOC specific emission rates (ER) of BAM and Eurofins for samples stored under different storage conditions. No trend was observed for any storage time or temperature. A gross measurement error occurred at BAM's measurement of the '23°14d' sample.

Since the storage does not seem to have any influence, we used the same results to calculate the in-batch reproducibility (**Table 5**). The tests were conducted at

two different laboratories and over 6 months, so it kind of resembles the top-down approach. This way, the reproducibility reveals the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure. Both partners produced very similar average emission rates and relative standard deviations. The relative standard deviations (24–33 %) of *n*-hexane, toluene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol are in a typical range for the emission test chamber procedure. The relative standard deviation (44 %) of D-limonene is probably overestimated. This might be due to the small *ER* of the μ -capsules (the absolute standard deviation of D-limonene is quite low). A higher material in-weight might lead to better results in the future.

Table 5. Results of the in-batch reproducibility (values taken from the investigation of storage conditions). The results of BAM and Eurofins are very similar. The relative standard deviation can be used as a measure for the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure.

	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonene
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM	21.5	31.2	23.0	9.5
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] Eurofins	22.4	30.4	19.9	13.2
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] both	21.9	30.8	21.4	11.4
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM	5.1	7.0	6.6	4.3
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] Eurofins	6.5	7.1	7.0	5.8
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] both	5.7	6.9	6.7	5.3
rel. SD [%] BAM	23.9	22.3	28.5	44.8
rel. SD [%] Eurofins	28.9	23.2	35.1	44.2
rel. SD [%] both	26.2	22.4	31.4	47.0

7 Results and discussion of ILCs

7.1 Results of ILC part 2 (ERMs)

The participants reported their analysis results by submitting the filled measurement protocol (all data concerning the ILC part 2 is found in **Annex 5.1**). The participants were asked to report VOC concentrations. These were then translated into the responding VOC specific emission rates (*ER*) by BAM.

Information about the chamber size and air exchange rate were provided by the participants beforehand, and the sample in-weight was known to BAM as organiser of the ILC part 2.

Additionally, BAM sent two tubes to each participant to be sampled right after the participants' sampling at day 14 for quality control. The emission rates of these tubes were also calculated. Two samplings were conducted with the participants' tubes and with BAM tubes respectively. It was checked, if the *ER* values of both samplings are congruent and, if not, which one is the more reliable value (e.g., checking the location within the calibrated range, or notes from the laboratory's personnel). Valid *ER* values of the participants and of the BAM tubes are depicted in **Figure 4**.

An evaluation of the laboratories' performance will not be given, because of the small number of participants (8 out of 10 reported results) and the relatively high variability of the results. When calculating the z score, all participants would be within $|z| \leq 2$. Instead, the results will only be shown and discussed.

Participant values and BAM tubes; *n*-hexane

Participant values and BAM tubes; toluene

Figure 4. VOC specific emission rates (ER) at day 14 of the ILC part 2 reported by the participants (blue) and BAM tubes (orange) sampled by the participants but analysed by BAM. The results of the participants were confirmed with help of the BAM tubes at least for *n*-hexane and toluene. D-limonene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol were only lowly abundant (close to or below the calibration) so that the results of these two substances can be hardly interpreted due to high uncertainties and/or only a few valid values.

When reviewing the data, it can be recognised that the concentrations (and ERs) of *n*-hexane, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene are quite low. Toluene, *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol were measured quite reliably, as it can be seen in **Figure 4**. D-limonene can be hardly interpreted due to the very low reliability of the values, caused by the very small emission rate of the material. The results of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol should be interpreted with caution. An explanation could be that toluene was usually in the centre of most calibrated ranges, *n*-hexane was often close to the lower limit (but within), while 2-ethyl-1-hexanol was often at the lower limit (barely within) and D-limonene was at or below the lowest calibrated standard. Of course, this depends highly on the participants' sampling volume and

calibrated range. Lab-06, Lab-07 and Lab-08 sampled higher volumes for the V2 sampling (4–5 L), which should result in more reliable values especially for 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene. The relative standard deviation of *n*-hexane (57 %) and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol (66 %) is high, and the relative standard deviation of toluene (18 %) is low. It was found in other ILC studies, that the relative standard deviations are in the range of 28–51 % (over all mean of all VOCs) [7]. Toluene, D-limonene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol are typically around 30 %.

The mean *ER* values of the BAM tubes are similar to the values reported by the participants. The variability of BAM tubes is lower in general, because of less uncertainty sources (e.g., different measurement devices). The differences (mean *ER*s and variabilities) are in the expected range/in the range of measurement uncertainty (**Table 6**).

Table 6. Mean VOC specific *ER* values and their variabilities of the participant's reports and of BAM tubes found during the ILC part 2.

	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	D-limonene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] participants	13.61	56.79	1.47 ^a	4.43 ^b
mean <i>ER</i> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM tubes	14.80	52.65	2.87 ^a	7.13 ^b
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] participants	7.70	10.17	0.52 ^a	2.92 ^b
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$] BAM tubes	6.85	7.61	0.69 ^a	2.38 ^b
rel. SD [%] participants	56.57	17.90	35.63 ^a	65.89 ^b
rel. SD [%] BAM tubes	46.29	14.45	24.05 ^a	33.32 ^b

^a Can be hardly interpreted. ^b Should be interpreted with caution – high uncertainty due to concentrations at the lower limit of the calibrated range.

The VOC specific *ER* value of the participants and of the respective BAM tube are congruent for toluene and *n*-hexane, while the values of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol are somewhat congruent. This is a particularly good finding: the participants' analysis methods are accurate (at least for reasonable VOC concentrations). The question is, however, what is causing the high variations of the *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated materials? Is it due to the material and/or due to the variability of the emission test chamber? Since the toluene impregnated material (C 40/4; powder) reveals only little variability, it can be assumed, that it might be a material specific behaviour at least for the *n*-hexane impregnated zeolite (BEA; powder). It is known from the development that the impregnation with 2-ethyl-1-

hexanol is difficult. This might lead to less homogeneity of the material, and it is likely the reason for the low *ER* of this batch. This low *ER* again leads to less reliable measurement values. Though the same base material was used for toluene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol behaves obviously differently during impregnation and likely during emission as well.

Usually, the μ -capsules emit a stable concentration over a very long time. The low *ER* ($\sim 1.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$ after 14 days) found during the ILC part 2 was surprising. The material was tested very similar to before (e.g., the internal validation; *ER* = $\sim 12 \mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$ after 28 days). Only the pre-aging was one week longer and conducted under 50 % rel. H. instead of dry air. A negative influence of this size is unlikely for the pre-aging. It could be, that the stored μ -capsule suspension aged.

It is difficult to compare the results of *n*-hexane, toluene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated materials from the internal validation with results obtained during the ILC part 2, because the porous base materials were different and/or were pre-processed (**Table 5** and **Table 6**). During the internal validation, only granulates of C 40/4 and C 45/4 were used. In the ILC part 2, powders of C 40/4 and BEA (zeolite) were used. A change from C 45/4 (granulate) to C 40/4 (powder) seems to slightly improve the variability of toluene impregnated porous materials. Which one of the two parameters is responsible here (change of type or powder/granulate), cannot be stated. The 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated materials showed worse results when changing from C 40/4 (granulate) to C 40/4 (powder), but as discussed above, this might be due to the difficulty during impregnation and measurement. The *n*-hexane impregnated BEA (powder) yields a worse variability than the C 45/4 (granulate).

8 Conclusion

The ERMs were validated in ILC part 2. At least one material (the toluene impregnated C 40/4 powder) performed very well. It has a reasonable emission rate and a low variability of only 18 %. This proves, that the laboratories' emission testing capabilities are generally good at least under less challenging conditions (i.e., reasonable chamber air concentration and toluene is usually easily detectable). Two other materials (*n*-hexane impregnated BEA powder and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 powder) showed low emission rates and high variabilities. It can be assumed, that parts of these findings are due to the material specific behaviour and due to the low emission rate, while both are mutually dependent on each other. The μ -capsules showed very unsatisfying results, i.e., very low emission and thus only a few valid measurement results were obtained.

The participants gave information about their emission testing and measurement methods. Most methods seem to be in good accordance with the standard. The best practice of using mass flow controllers/meters for sampling was used by all participants. However, more emphasis should be on the estimation of uncertainty. It might lead to improvement and higher transparency of the results. It is further advised to adjust the sampling volume in such a way that the estimated VOC concentration in the emission chamber is within the calibrated range of the analytical system.

Annex 5.1 Chamber sizes and sample in-weights of partners and participants

A5.1.1 Chamber sizes

The used chamber sizes of participants of the ILC part 2 are given in **Table 7**.

Table 7. Chamber sizes of the ILC part 2 participants.

Participant (ILC part 2)	Chamber size [L]	Air exchange rate [h^{-1}]
Lab-01	230	0.5
Lab-03	20	0.5
Lab-04	500	0.5
Lab-05	125	0.5
Lab-06	225	0.5
Lab-07	270	0.5
Lab-08	119	0.5
Lab-10	250	0.5

A5.1.2 Sample in-weights

The sample in-weights of the ERMs used in the ILC part 2 are given in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Sample in-weights of ERMs used in the ILC part 2.

Participant (ILC part 2)	Material	VOC	m [g] per package
Lab-01	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.1528
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.1504
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.1791
	μ -capsules	D-limonene	2 petri dishes ^a
Lab-03	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.1445
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.2225
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.2124
	μ -capsules	D-limonene	1 petri dish ^a
Lab-04	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.2563
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.2371
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.3500
	μ -capsules	D-limonene	4 petri dishes ^a
Lab-05	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.1350
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.1662
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.2095
	μ -capsules	D-limonene	1 petri dish ^a
Lab-06	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.1463
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.2412
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.2250

	μ-capsules	D-limonene	1 petri dish ^a
Lab-07	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.1450
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.2350
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.2106
	μ-capsules	D-limonene	2 petri dishes ^a
Lab-08	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.1590
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.1743
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.1509
	μ-capsules	D-limonene	1 petri dish ^a
Lab-10	BEA (powder)	n-hexane	0.2083
	C 40/4 (powder)	toluene	0.2460
	C 40/4 (powder)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	0.2193
	μ-capsules	D-limonene	2 petri dishes ^a

^a One petri dish contains 1.357 mL aqueous μ-capsule suspension with 6.8 w% capsules.

A5.1.3 Sampling volumes

The sampling volumes of ILC part 2 are given in **Table 9**. The sampling volumes of BAM tubes, sampled in addition to the regular sampling during the ILC part 2, are given in **Table 10**. Since the data interpretation focuses on the last day of the emission testing (day 14), only volumes of this day are given.

Table 9. Sampling volumes of the ERM emission tests of the ILC part 2. Only the sampling volume after 336 h (14 days) is given.

Day / V#	Sampling volumes [L]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	1.00	0.97	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.08	2.28	1.00
Day 14 V2	2.00	2.04	2.00	2.00	4.00	4.60	5.19	2.00

Table 10. Sampling volumes of BAM tubes sampled during the ERM emission test (ILC part 2). The tubes were sampled in addition to the regular sampling by the participants and send back to BAM for analysis. Two tubes were provided to sample on day 14 (336 h after loading the ERMs into the emission test chamber).

Day / V#	Sampling volumes [L]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	2.00	0.97	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.08	2.28	1.09
Day 14 V2	2.00	2.04	2.00	2.00	4.00	4.60	5.19	2.00

A5.1.4 Measurement results

Results (concentrations) of the ILC part 2 are given in **Table 11** (*n*-hexane), **Table 12** (toluene), **Table 13** (2-ethyl-1-hexanol) and **Table 14** (D-limonene). Results (mass on the respective tube, measured by TD-GC-FID at BAM) of the additionally loaded BAM tubes can be found in **Table 15** (*n*-hexane), **Table 16** (toluene), **Table 17** (2-ethyl-1-hexanol) and **Table 18** (D-limonene). Only results of day 14 (336 h after loading the ERMs into the emission test chamber) are given.

Table 11. Measurement results (concentration of VOC in the chamber air provided by the participants) of the ILC part 2 (VOC = *n*-hexane); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Concentration of <i>n</i> -hexane [ng/L] <-> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	8.00	216.15	24.00	25.00	40.00	13.77 ^a	30.60	22.63
Day 14 V2	7.00	264.29	24.00	24.00	33.00	9.82	23.60	20.16

^a Below the lowest calibration standard.

Table 12. Measurement results (concentration of VOC in the chamber air provided by the participants) of the ILC part 2 (VOC = toluene); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Concentration of toluene [ng/L] <-> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	71.00	1205.41	53.00	147.00	167.00	100.82	136.00	108.31
Day 14 V2	71.00	1346.16	51.00	153.00	156.00	97.20	150.00	97.79

Table 13. Measurement results (concentration of VOC in the chamber air provided by the participants) of the ILC part 2 (VOC = 2-ethyl-1-hexanol); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Concentration of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol [ng/L] <-> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	12.00	40.29 ^a	4.00	17.00	2.00	15.09 ^b	13.60	2.04
Day 14 V2	15.00	28.61 ^a	5.00	20.00	3.00	8.19	10.20	1.83

^a Not baseline separated from D-limonene. ^b Below the lowest calibration standard.

Table 14. Measurement results (concentration of VOC in the chamber air provided by the participants) of the ILC part 2 (VOC = D-limonene); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Concentration of D-limonene [ng/L] <-> [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	< 5 ^a	4.45 ^b	2.00	2.00	< 1 ^a	7.39 ^c	3.37	2.58
Day 14 V2	< 5 ^a	5.53 ^b	2.00	2.00	< 1 ^a	3.25 ^c	1.96	1.50

^a These values cannot be considered for further calculations. ^b Not baseline separated from 2-ethyl-1-hexanol. ^c Below lowest calibration standard.

Table 15. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by BAM) of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 (VOC = n-hexane); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Mass of n-hexane [ng]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	17.60	236.73	23.82	26.56	71.43	14.86 ^a	78.14	17.60 ^a
Day 14 V2	17.50	7.49	43.54	47.47	122.59	45.12	155.99	17.50

^a Below the lowest calibration standard.

Table 16. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by BAM) of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 (VOC = toluene); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Mass of toluene [ng]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	121.43	1296.22	45.19	148.86	281.15	108.75	318.19	120.35
Day 14 V2	120.33	27.54	82.92	280.48	465.80	446.66	739.50	215.81

Table 17. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by BAM) of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 (VOC = 2-ethyl-1-hexanol); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Mass of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol [ng]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	34.72	37.75	16.34 ^a	34.96	23.97	16.28 ^a	48.94	15.43 ^a
Day 14 V2	34.73	11.55	21.40	56.57	33.21	37.65	103.04	19.11

^a Below the lowest calibration standard.

Table 18. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by BAM) of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 (VOC = D-limonene); sampled on day 14.

Day / V#	Mass of D-limonene [ng]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	9.66 ^a	9.30 ^a	9.98 ^a	7.92 ^a	8.09 ^a	7.97 ^a	8.97 ^a	8.45 ^a
Day 14 V2	9.54 ^a	6.07 ^a	10.67	9.59 ^a	9.63	14.94	12.76	9.99 ^a

^a Below the lowest calibration standard.

A5.1.5 Emission rates of the ILC part 2

The measurement results of the ILC part 2 were translated into emission rates (ER) according to the equation given in chapter 4.3.1. ERs of the ILC part 2 are given in **Table 19** (*n*-hexane), **Table 20** (toluene), **Table 21** (2-ethyl-1-hexanol) and **Table 22** (D-limonene). Results of the additionally loaded BAM tubes can be found in **Table 23** (*n*-hexane), **Table 24** (toluene), **Table 25** (2-ethyl-1-hexanol) and **Table 26** (D-limonene). Only results of day 14 (336 h after loading the ERMs into the emission test chamber) are given.

Table 19. Emission rates of the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = *n*-hexane).

Day / V#	ER of <i>n</i> -hexane [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	6.02	18.44	23.41	11.57	30.76	12.82 ^a	11.45	13.58
Day 14 V2	5.27	22.55	23.41	11.11	25.38	9.14	8.83	12.10

^a Below the lowest calibration standard.

Table 20. Emission rates of the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = toluene).

Day / V#	ER of toluene [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	54.29	76.58	55.88	55.28	77.89	57.92	46.43	55.04
Day 14 V2	54.29	85.52	53.77	57.54	72.76	55.84	51.20	49.69

Table 21. Emission rates of the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = 2-ethyl-1-hexanol).

Day / V#	ER of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	7.71	1.82 ^a	2.86 ^b	5.07	1.00	9.67 ^b	5.36	1.16 ^b
Day 14 V2	9.63	1.29 ^a	3.57	5.97	1.50	5.25	4.02	1.04

^a Not baseline separated from 2-ethyl-1-hexanol. ^b Below lowest calibration standard.

Table 22. Emission rates of the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = D-limonene).

Day / V#	ER of D-limonene [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	< 3.12 ^a	0.48 ^b	1.35	1.35	< 1.22 ^a	5.40 ^c	2.17	1.74
Day 14 V2	< 3.12 ^a	0.60 ^b	1.35	1.35	< 1.22 ^a	2.38 ^c	1.26	1.01

^a Cannot be used due to "<". ^b Not baseline separated from 2-ethyl-1-hexanol. ^c Below lowest calibration standard.

Table 23. Emission rates of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = n-hexane).

Day / V#	ER of n-hexane [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	6.62	20.92	23.23	12.30	27.47	12.82	12.85	22.62
Day 14 V2	6.58	0.31	21.24	10.99	23.57	9.14	11.25	20.87

Table 24. Emission rates of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = toluene).

Day / V#	ER of toluene [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	46.42	85.29	47.65	55.98	65.57	57.92	47.74	55.95
Day 14 V2	46.00	0.86	43.72	52.74	54.31	55.84	48.64	54.86

Table 25. Emission rates of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = 2-ethyl-1-hexanol).

Day / V#	ER of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	11.15	1.77	11.67 ^a	10.43	5.99	9.67 ^a	8.48	8.05 ^a
Day 14 V2	11.15	0.26	7.64	8.44	4.15	5.25	7.83	5.45

^c Below lowest calibration standard.

Table 26. Emission rates of BAM tubes sampled during the ILC part 2 calculated based on the information given above (VOC = D-limonene).

Day / V#	ER of D-limonene [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\times\text{g}$]							
	Lab-01	Lab-03	Lab-04	Lab-05	Lab-06	Lab-07	Lab-08	Lab-10
Day 14 V1	3.01 ^a	1.04 ^a	6.76 ^a	5.36 ^a	4.93 ^a	5.40 ^a	2.54 ^a	5.24 ^a
Day 14 V2	2.97 ^a	0.32 ^a	3.61	3.25 ^a	2.93	2.38	1.58	3.38 ^a

^c Below lowest calibration standard.

References

1. EN, *Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Determination of emissions into indoor air (EN 16516:2017+A1:2020)*. 2020, European Committee for Standardization (CEN): DIN Media, Berlin.
2. de Krom, I., et al., *Guideline for the preparation and analysis of gPRMs and gCRMs of indoor air pollutants stated in the EU-LCI list with relative uncertainties below 5 % ($k = 2$) and a shelf life of at least 1 year - Deliverable D3 of the EMPIR project 20NRM04 MetrIAQ*. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10656469>
3. ISO, *Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison (ISO 13528:2022)*. 2022, International Organization for Standardization DIN Media, Berlin.
4. ISO, *Gas analysis – Comparison methods for the determination of the composition of gas mixtures based on one- and two-point calibration (ISO 12963:2017)*. 2017, International Organization for Standardization DIN Media, Berlin.
5. ISO, *Conformity assessment - General requirements for the competence of proficiency testing providers (ISO/IEC 17043:2023)*. 2023, International Organization for Standardization DIN Media, Berlin.
6. Ellison, S.L.R., A. Williams, and (eds.), *EURACHEM/CITAC Guide CG 4 - Quantifying Uncertainty in Analytical Measurement, 3rd edition*. 2012.
7. Wilke, O., et al., *Volatile organic compounds from building products—Results from six round robin tests with emission test chambers conducted between 2008 and 2018*. *Indoor Air*, 2021. **31**(6): p. 2049-2057.